

European Cloud for Heritage Open Science

Deliverable D4.1 Report on identification of communities and their needs

HORIZON-CL2-2023-HERITAGE-ECCCH-01

Horizon Innovation action

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Project start	1 June 2024
Project duration	60 months
Document Identifier	10.5281/zenodo.20441283

**Funded by
the European Union**

**UK Research
and Innovation**

ECHOES is a project funded by the European Commission under Grant Agreement n.101157364, with the support of UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee n.10110142 & n.10110466.

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Deliverable Information

Project Number	101157364	Acronym	ECHOES
Full title	European Cloud for Heritage OpEn Science		
Project URL	https://www.echoes-ecch.eu/		
EU Project Officer	Christian WILK		

Deliverable	D4.1	Title	Report on identification of communities and their needs
Work Package	WP4	Title	Building a New Community
Submission date	29/05/2026		
Pages	pp. 128	Keywords	Cultural Heritage communities, User needs analysis, Community consultation

Lead Partner	ARIADNE RI		
Responsible Author	Claudio Prandoni		
Change log			
Date	Version	Author	Change
13/03/2026	v0.1	C. Prandoni	First draft including what has been drafted so far in an internal working document
13/04/2026	v0.2	All authors	First consolidated draft ready for review
30/04/2026	v0.3	All authors	Second consolidated draft ready for review
19/05/2026	v0.9	All authors	Final version
29/05/2026	v1.0	Xavier Rodier	Final proofreading, and submission to the ECH
01/06/2026	v1.1	Nora Tufenkjian	Fixed minor editing issues

Disclaimer: Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

AI tools were used in the preparation of this document: ChatGPT was used to review and improve the English of selected passages; Grammarly, DeepL and ChatGPT were used for data exploitation; GitHub Copilot was used as a coding assistance tool during the development of the interactive dashboard and web apps. All outputs generated by these tools were reviewed for accuracy and were revised as necessary before inclusion in the document.

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Abstract

This deliverable presents the results of the activities carried out within Work Package 4 of the ECHOES project to identify, characterise and engage cultural heritage communities, with the objective of informing the design and development of the Cultural Heritage Cloud (ECCCH).

The report is based on a mixed-method and iterative approach combining large-scale quantitative data collection through an international survey, qualitative analysis of open-ended responses, and targeted validation through workshops, focus groups and complementary consultation activities. This approach enabled both a broad mapping of the cultural heritage landscape and an in-depth understanding of community practices, needs and expectations.

The analysis highlights the diversity and hybridity of cultural heritage communities, identifying a set of transversal needs shared across profiles, such as interoperability, accessibility of tools, data governance, and capacity building, as well as more specific requirements linked to distinct professional roles and levels of digital maturity. These insights are synthesised through the development of an Atlas of communities and personas, providing a structured and human-centred framework to support user-centred design.

The report also includes a gap analysis comparing identified needs with existing tools and emerging solutions developed within the Cloud ecosystem, highlighting both areas of progress and remaining systemic challenges. The results underline that the development of the Cultural Heritage Cloud cannot rely solely on technological solutions, but requires a holistic, user-centred and ecosystem-based approach that integrates infrastructure, services, governance, and capacity building.

These insights provide a foundation for the next phase of the project, contributing to the strategic development of the Cloud and informing future actions in WP4 and beyond, such as the definition of technical requirements, community engagement strategies, integration and onboarding processes, and capacity building activities across ECHOES and the broader Cloud ecosystem.

The consultation process itself also constitutes a key outcome, establishing an initial network of engaged stakeholders and setting the basis for a continuous, iterative dialogue with cultural heritage communities throughout the lifetime of the project.

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List of abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CCI	Cultural and Creative Industries
CH	Cultural Heritage
DOA	Description of Action
ECCCH	European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage aka Cultural Heritage Cloud
ECHOES	European Cloud for Heritage OpEn Science
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GLAMs	Galleries, Libraries, Archives, and Museums
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IT	Information Technologies
LOD	Linked Open Data
PAIR	Projects, Actors, Ideas, Resources
RI	Research Infrastructure
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

The ECHOES project aims to support the design, development and adoption of the European Cultural Heritage Cloud by placing cultural heritage communities and their practices at the centre of the process. In this context, understanding who these communities are, how they currently work with digital data, tools and services, and what they expect from a shared digital infrastructure is a prerequisite for building a sustainable, useful and widely adopted Cloud ecosystem.

Deliverable D4.1, *Report on Identification of Communities and Their Needs*, documents the work carried out within Work Package 4 during the first two years of the project (June 2024 – May 2026) to map, analyse and validate the needs and expectations of cultural heritage communities in relation to the future Cultural Heritage Cloud. The deliverable brings together a series of complementary activities, combining a large-scale quantitative questionnaire with qualitative and participatory approaches, to provide an evidence-based and community-informed foundation for subsequent technical, organisational and capacity building work within ECHOES.

Rather than focusing on a single category of users, the approach adopted in WP4 recognises the diversity and hybridity of the cultural heritage landscape. Cultural heritage professionals operate across multiple sectors, disciplines and institutional settings, often combining roles related to research, documentation, conservation, communication, management and technical development. D4.1 therefore seeks to capture this diversity, identifying recurring patterns of practice and shared challenges while also accounting for community-specific contexts and constraints.

The results presented in this deliverable are intended to inform multiple dimensions of the project. They support the definition of early requirements and working hypotheses for the technical development of the Cloud, contribute to integration and onboarding strategies for communities and projects, and provide key input for the design of training and capacity building activities. At the same time, the consultation process itself constitutes an important engagement mechanism, fostering dialogue with future users and establishing the basis for longer-term collaboration between the project and cultural heritage communities.

1.1 Objectives of Deliverable D4.1

The main objectives of Deliverable D4.1 are to:

- Identify and characterise the communities working on, with or around cultural heritage that constitute current or potential future users of the Cultural Heritage Cloud.
- Analyse the digital practices of these communities, including their use of data, tools, services and infrastructures, as well as their levels of digital literacy and maturity.
- Capture communities' needs, expectations and concerns in relation to digital infrastructures, tools and services, with particular attention to barriers, gaps and unmet needs.
- Assess the findings of the [questionnaire](#)¹ through iterative engagement with communities, including workshops, focus groups and interviews.
- Synthesise the results into an integrated Atlas of communities, needs and expectations that can be used across the project.

The deliverable does not aim to define detailed technical specifications or implementation strategies. Instead, it provides an analytical and evidential basis that feeds into subsequent strategic and operational work, notably Deliverable D4.2 on the strategy for community building and engagement.

¹ The questionnaire is available as an additional document, complementary to this deliverable.

1.2 Relationship with other Work Packages

Deliverable D4.1 is designed as a transversal resource for the ECHOES project. Its outputs directly inform and support the work of several other Work Packages:

- WP2 (Communication, Dissemination, Engagement) draws from the work on CH communities to tailor communication, dissemination and engagement activities to the communities they are destined to.
- WP3 (Integration and onboarding) uses the community mapping and profiling to support the integration of external projects and initiatives into the Cultural Heritage Cloud and to tailor engagement and collaboration mechanisms. In addition, Task 3.1 carried out a comprehensive gap analysis to identify which existing datasets, tools and workflows developed in previously funded European, national and regional cultural heritage projects align with the needs of the communities identified through the consultation (see Section 5.3).
- WP5 (Capacity building and training) draws on the identified needs and digital skill gaps to design targeted training pathways and capacity building resources adapted to different communities and levels of digital maturity.
- Technical Work Packages (WP6 to WP9) benefit from insights into user practices, priorities and constraints, which help frame early requirements, guide design choices and support user-centred development of infrastructure, semantics, assessment frameworks and services.
- WP10 (Cloud governance) taps into the results of WP4 activities to better include and represent CH communities in the future governance and legal entity of the Cloud, for instance, through the future Community Advisory Board.
- WP11 (Long-term sustainability) benefits from a clearer understanding of value chains, stakeholder roles and long-term community engagement dynamics.

By consolidating evidence across these dimensions, D4.1 acts as a shared reference point for aligning technical development, engagement strategies and capacity building efforts across the project.

1.3 Methodological approach

The work presented in this deliverable is based on an integrated and iterative methodological framework that combines multiple sources of evidence and forms of engagement. Rather than relying on a single method, WP4 adopted a mixed approach to balance breadth of coverage with depth of understanding and to ensure continuous validation with the communities concerned.

The overall workflow includes the following main phases:

- **Mapping of interest (2023-2024):** analysis of letters of interest to identify organisations, sectors and activities potentially relevant to the Cultural Heritage Cloud.
- **Internal consultation (2024):** collection and review of existing surveys, reports and resources produced by ECHOES partners and related initiatives.
- **State-of-the-art review (2024-2025):** comparison with sister projects and external sources addressing community mapping, digital practices and skills.
- **Survey design and implementation (2024-2025):** development, testing, dissemination and administration of the ECHOES Consultation questionnaire.
- **Quantitative and qualitative analysis (2025):** statistical analysis of closed questions and structured analysis of open-ended responses.
- **Community clustering and persona development (2025):** identification of recurring user profiles and synthesis of findings into human-centred analytical tools.
- **Complementary consultation activities (2025-2026):** validation and deepening of results through workshops and focus groups, as well as participation and contribution to other project activities such as collaborative research scenario workshops.
- **Atlas and needs synthesis (2026):** integration of results into a consolidated view of communities, needs and expectations.

This methodological approach allows the project to move from exploratory mapping to validated insights, while maintaining flexibility to adapt and refine the analysis as new feedback and evidence emerge.

2. Baseline knowledge

2.1 Mapping of interest

During the preparation of the proposal to the HORIZON-CL2-2023-HERITAGE-ECCCH-01 call, the Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique, the Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, and the Fondation des Sciences du Patrimoine launched on 22 May 2023 a call to map the stakeholders' interest in the future Cultural Heritage Cloud.

Until 15 July 2023, institutions, professionals, and researchers had the opportunity to submit a letter to express their interest in benefiting from ECHOES's digital tools and services and/or contribute to it by sharing their data. 247 letters were received, with a majority from France, Italy and Portugal.

The information collected from these letters was compiled into a spreadsheet outlining the institution's name, typology, cultural heritage sector and activities (based on the first version of the Atlas of communities depicted in the figure below), country, and links to other partners.

Figure 1: First version of the Atlas of the communities

This dataset was subsequently explored through an interactive dashboard developed using Power BI, enabling a more detailed analysis of geographic and institutional distributions, as well as the identification of dominant domain sectors (Ex.: "Preservation, Protection"; "Interpretation, Understanding", ...), activities (Ex.: "Inventorying, cataloguing"; "Visualization"; "Teaching"; etc.) and organisation types (Ex.: "Museum"; "University"; etc). The dashboard is structured into main sections – domain sector, activity, and type of organisation – each complemented by geographic maps to visualise the distribution of contributions across countries, and an additional section displaying the primary cultural sector.

The analysis highlights a strong concentration of institutions in a limited number of countries. France clearly dominates the dataset, with 59 in organisation types, 167 in activities, and 98 in domains. It is followed by Italy (43 organisation types, 64 activities, and 53 domains) and Portugal (24 organisation types, 52 activities, and 41 domains). Other countries such as the United Kingdom, Austria, Spain, and Germany are also represented, although with significantly lower frequencies.

From a sectoral perspective, Archaeology is the most represented field (31 occurrences), followed by Libraries (15) and Archives (14).

Figure 2: Primary cultural heritage sector

In terms of organisation types, universities are predominant (54), followed by private companies (24) and joint research units (21), highlighting the strong involvement of academic institutions alongside industry and collaborative research structures.

Figure 3: Organisation type

Overall, the Power BI dashboard provides an effective tool for exploring these dimensions in depth, offering both quantitative and geographic first insights into the structure and composition of the Cultural Heritage Cloud community.

To identify the communities' needs and offers presented in these letters, the exploitation of the Mapping of interest was carried out by complementary approaches. While the identification of relevant terms can be reliably automated, determining the intent behind each mention remains more challenging. Most letters describe past or ongoing projects

rather than explicitly stated needs, which results in a predominance of implicit offers of tools, services, or expertise. The aim of the analysis was therefore to structure this information in a way that supports its reuse within the project.

A study was carried out to develop a methodology for the automatic extraction of references to tools and services from letters of interest, as well as the classification of the intent associated with each mention. The intent was categorised into “Offer” and “Need”. The large-scale application of the extraction and classification pipeline to the full corpus of letters of interest provided a comprehensive overview of the distribution of identified intents.

The results confirm the strong predominance of the *Offer* category already observed during manual evaluation, reflecting the declarative nature of the letters, which primarily emphasise existing contributions, expertise, and available resources. Conversely, explicit expressions of *Need* remain relatively limited, while the *Neutral* category is almost absent, further highlighting the difficulty of identifying statements that do not clearly convey intent. We did not analyse in depth these *Offers*, as they are understood just as a demonstration of people's interest in working with the Cloud.

The study highlights both strengths and limitations of the tool. Term extraction proved robust and reliable, forming a solid foundation, while intent classification remained challenging, particularly for the underrepresented Need and context-dependent Neutral categories.

In conclusion, while substantial progress was made to extract and identify classes, future work should focus on refining models to handle implicit and nuanced language. The analysis of the Mapping of Interest demonstrates the geographic scope of the first communities willing to support and shape the Cloud's development, bringing their expertise and resources to contribute to the initiative. A complementary cartography, based on the results of this activity, is being developed to present the continuous growth to the Cultural Heritage Cloud ecosystem (See section 3.4.3 “CartoECHOES”).

2.2 Internal consultation with partners

The internal consultation with project partners was designed to systematically map existing initiatives, tools and practices relevant to community mapping and engagement, to carry out needs assessment and data collection within the heritage domain. This internal enquiry was developed in cooperation with Task 3.1 “Gap analysis and integration strategy reusing datasets, tools and workflows in ECHOES” and Task 5.1 “Identify capacity building needs, gaps and existing resources of the communities”. The aim was to gather existing initiatives that had mapped the key communities of professionals active in the fields of tangible, intangible and digital heritage, capturing the diversity of fields of expertise, practices and the methodologies used across the public and private sectors, professional associations, non-profit organisations and citizen-led initiatives.

This exercise also sought to identify communities' needs and gaps in terms of skills, capacity building opportunities, practices, tools, workflows and resources as they navigate the digital transition of the heritage sector.

To this end, a structured data collection template was developed and shared with all partners. The template enabled partners to report on relevant projects and initiatives they were involved in or aware of, covering several key dimensions:

- Existence and characteristics of existing surveys dedicated to understanding the wider heritage community and their needs.
- Prior mapping exercises of communities or stakeholders.
- Types of communities involved or targeted.
- Heritage domains addressed.
- Existence and features of databases or digital platforms supporting data collection and analysis.

The consultation resulted in the collection of inputs describing over 30 initiatives spanning European and international contexts that informed ECHOES survey design and further mapping exercises. The gathered evidence shows a strong prevalence of prior experience in both survey-based data collection and community mapping exercises, often combined with the development of digital infrastructures for data aggregation and access. These initiatives cover a wide spectrum of heritage domains and related fields of practice, including cultural heritage research and its infrastructures; study, conservation, management and use of heritage; digital humanities and other social sciences; GLAM institutions, built and archaeological environments; infrastructures in the field of musicology and repositories as well as those active in IT development.

From a methodological perspective, several *recurring* approaches emerged. First, many initiatives rely on mixed-method consultation strategies, combining structured surveys with qualitative inputs such as workshops, interviews or community forums. Second, there is a clear tendency to target heterogeneous and multi-layered communities, ranging from researchers and heritage professionals to aggregators, institutions, and, in some cases, broader user groups beyond the heritage sector. Third, multiple projects made efforts to use controlled vocabularies, taxonomies or classification schemes to ensure consistency in data collection and to enable comparability across datasets, notwithstanding the inherent difficulties to overcome the high technical, semantical specificities of heritage domains and practices.

At the same time, the analysis highlighted several challenges and gaps. These include fragmentation in the definition and categorisation of communities and how their professional practice is described, limited interoperability between existing datasets and platforms, and uneven coverage across heritage domains and stakeholder groups.

In several cases, surveys and mapping exercises are tailored to specific project needs and mandates, limiting their reusability and comparability.

The insights derived from this internal consultation directly informed the design of the ECHOES survey. In particular, they supported:

- The identification of relevant community categories and stakeholder groups.
- The definition of key thematic areas to be addressed in the questionnaire.
- The adoption of a mixed-method approach combining quantitative and qualitative data collection.
- The need to ensure interoperability and reusability of the collected data through standardised structures and vocabularies.

2.3 Relevant examples and best practices

This section presents a more in-depth analysis of ongoing or closed projects considered relevant examples & best practices, which were used as a starting point and informed the design of the ECHOES survey.

ESPADON – General Survey of Cultural Heritage Data

ESPADON (2021 – 2029) is a French project funded by the French *Agence Nationale de la Recherche* (ANR-ESRE-0050) to develop an instrumental and digital platform for Heritage Science and to support local Cultural Heritage institutions and research laboratories in their digital transition. It is coordinated by the

Fondation des Sciences du Patrimoine (FSP) and includes a large number of institutions from the French Ministry of Culture, CNRS, and universities.

In September 2021, ESPADON launched a “General Survey of Cultural Heritage Data”² at the national level to better understand the various digital needs of Cultural Heritage professionals and researchers in France, inform the development of its Digital platform and tools and refine its concept of “Augmented Digital Objects”.

This General Survey was structured into two phases: a questionnaire, which received more than 1100 responses (including 310 complete responses), and a series of nine domain-specific workshops on target communities co-chaired by project participants and field specialists over three years. These fields of activity included conservation-restoration and preventive conservation; curators; documentalists; heritage scientists; cultural heritage mediation; architects and built heritage professionals; anthropologists; art historians; and archaeologists.

² Thomas, R., et. al. (2026) *Etats généraux du patrimoine. Rapport final*.

The ESPADON General Survey, which included its questionnaire and workshop approach, was a direct inspiration for the design of the ECHOES Consultation. In particular, the ESPADON questionnaire served as the basis for developing the ECHOES questionnaire (see section 3).

Throughout WP4 activities, frequent exchanges were held with the ESPADON coordination team, which provided insights and advice on organising the ECHOES Consultation and exploiting the results.

ATRIUM – Skillset and Training Needs Assessment

 ATRIUM and ECHOES projects are both anchored in the principles of Open Science and FAIR, aiming to advance the digital transformation, assets and foster collaboration between academia, practitioners and service providers.

To identify the gap between the skills required to use advanced infrastructure services and the everyday needs of the research community, the ATRIUM Skills Assessment used two complementary questionnaires³: one targeting ATRIUM service providers and another one directed at researchers in Arts, Humanities, and Social Sciences.

- The Service Providers' questionnaire aimed to identify the target audiences, required skills, existing training resources, and potential barriers to the adoption of ATRIUM Services.
- The Researchers' survey was structured around five key sections: Demographics and Background, Research Activities, Open Science and FAIR Principles, Skills needed for the ATRIUM services, and Training Needs and Challenges in Online Learning.

The survey findings revealed significant gaps in advanced technical skills required to effectively use infrastructure services (e.g. APIs, programming, and command-line tools), alongside a strong demand for practical training in core data competencies and the applied use of Open Science and FAIR principles.

The ATRIUM structured approach of mapping professional practices and unmet needs through targeted surveys served as a precursor to the ECHOES WP4 Strategy, which adopted a similar but broader methodology to identify the workflows, expectations, and requirements of its own fragmented communities.

³ Delmazo, C., et al. (2025) *The ATRIUM Skillset Assessment and Gap Analysis Report*.

CHARTER – Heritage occupations framework

EUROPEAN CULTURAL
HERITAGE SKILLS
ALLIANCE

[CHARTER](#) (2021-2024) was an Erasmus+ project for the heritage sector with the aim of creating a comprehensive skills strategy for heritage professionals, to resolve the mismatches between education and training offer and labour

market needs. It mapped heritage activities and skills, necessary to describe existing and emerging professions and the related education provision.

Informed by previous research on CCIs, CHARTER proposed a model to describe the heritage sector, based on groups of activities aggregated by similarity of purpose – functions. The project suggested a circular value chain with three core heritage functions and three systemic ones.

These are: recognition (activities necessary to identification, study, inventory, documentation, formal recognition and advocacy for heritage recognition); preservation & safeguarding (activities necessary to ensure long-term sustainable care, including maintenance, conservation-restoration, preventive conservation or safeguard measure for intangible assets); engagement & use (activities necessary to make heritage understandable, open, accessible and available for use, consultation to all, includes actions of raising awareness to reach the broad community); management (activities necessary for strategic planning to everyday administration including organisational development, human resources management, funding mechanisms, organisational risk management and internal quality control); governance & policy-making (activities necessary in the decision-making and strategy design for the wide heritage domain including policy-making at all levels of governance); research & development and education (activities necessary to support innovation and technological development, capacity building, knowledge sharing and transfer throughout the all heritage value-chain). The functions translate clusters of activities with similar purposes, hence share tasks and present akin workflows, professionals operating within a function also manifest similar skills.

CHARTER also developed education and training pathways for curricula development to answer skills gaps, labour market demands responding to global challenges, organised in six pathways: community engagement; sustainability in built heritage and landscape; cultural heritage crafts and knowledge; new heritage in conservation-restoration; participatory leadership and management; and cultural heritage in the digital environment. Parallel to this work, it also conducted a wide survey to map occupations in the heritage sector, using ISCO-08 and national occupational catalogues as referent: enquired its profiles descriptions, main function served, EQF levels and other information relevant to fully comprehend professional profiles.

CHARTER work and proposals differ from ECHOES, as they are focused on heritage practice per se and not necessarily on the needs and requirements to operate within the digital environment.

Nevertheless, it does deliver a matrix to map heritage occupations, clustered professionals' activities and has identified major skills needs, with attention to the digital transformation in some expertise fields.

PERCEIVE Project

The logo for the PERCEIVE project. The word "PERCEIVE" is written in a bold, sans-serif font. The letter 'C' is stylized with a colorful, multi-colored circular graphic behind it, transitioning from blue to green to yellow to red.

[PERCEIVE](#) project, Perceptive Enhanced Realities of Colored collections through AI and Virtual Experiences aimed at advancing

the digital capability of scientists and cultural institutions through a service-based AI architecture and toolkit, and by developing a new design theory for on-site and remote VR/AR/MR experiences, based on the concepts of “Care”, “Accessibility”, and “Authenticity”, with and for the creative industries, expanding the access to Cultural Heritage and Art outside museums for wider integration with society.

The project addressed the fragility and the dual needs of better preserving and communicating coloured artwork (paintings, sculptures, textiles, historical films and photos and born-digital art) by improving and speeding up scientific process results, which could be employed to enhance preservation and maximise visitors' experience.

Based on the PERCEIVE theory of colour perception, study and representation, and the concepts of caring, authenticity and engagement, user needs and expectations were analysed in relation to PERCEIVE research and application scenarios.^{4 5}

The requirements for each digital tool were formulated based on the specific needs of various stakeholders. Stakeholders were categorised into six groups: 1) Museum Professionals, 2) Heritage Scientists, 3) Creative industries / Designers, 4) Citizens / Museum visitors, 5) Educators, 6) Decision Makers.

Their needs were mapped against key activities referring to Colour studies workflows and behaviours, including: material characterisation and colour change detection; scientific analysis and acquisition (shape, colour and material acquisitions and diagnostics); interpretation; colour change monitoring (sensitivity detection, exhibition policy); reality-based reconstruction (2d and 3d reconstruction of shape, material, color); conservation vs access policy (identification and mitigation of risks); communication of results (experts & public audience); data transparency of processes and reliability of results.

⁴ Pescarin, S., et al. (2023) *Perceiving Coloured Collections: the PERCEIVE theory*.

⁵ Pescarin S., et al. (eds.) (2025) *Chromatic Visions, Exploring Colour in Art, Archaeology and Digital Realities, Part I*.

For each activity, the following was considered: main issues professionals face; involvement of different actors/professionals; complexity of the activity; required Input data; produced output data

After an extended survey, an insightful analysis of the user requirements, based on a prioritisation process, was carried out and evolved by the working group of each scenario, using a composite methodological approach combining:

- a. The PACT method (People, Activity, Context, Technology) and it is a way to enquire and let relevant elements emerge to define and prioritise the needs for each PERCEIVE tool or prototype, interrogating the relevant stakeholders (People), their context (Context), workflow/behaviours (Activities), needs, acceptable and available tools and services (Technologies) and requirements.
- b. The Cultural Probe Kits (CPK)^{6 7}.

The insights derived from this process, including the structured mapping of stakeholder needs against colour studies workflows and the prioritisation of tool requirements, represent a relevant methodological reference for the community engagement work carried out within ECHOES WP4. Full data is available in the public report.⁸

The work carried out in PERCEIVE directly feeds into [COLOURS](#) (Collaborative On-cloud Lab for the conservation and digital Restoration of Coloured heritage collectionS), an ECHOES sister project that builds on PERCEIVE's tools and methodology to develop a cloud-based toolkit for the conservation and restoration of coloured cultural heritage. By extending the PERCEIVE approach into the Cultural Heritage Cloud environment, COLOURS targets conservators and restoration professionals as its primary user community. For this deliverable, it is particularly relevant that COLOURS adopts a community-first approach in its early phases, engaging conservators-restorers directly to verify their needs and define requirements before tool development proceeds. This approach resonates with the community engagement methodology adopted in ECHOES WP4, confirming the relevance of stakeholder-centred design as a shared principle across the Cultural Heritage Cloud ecosystem.

⁶ Benyon, D., et al. (2005). *Designing interactive systems: People, activities, contexts, technologies*.

⁷ Pescarin, S., et al. (2023) *PERCEIVE Cultural Probe Kit on Caring attitude in XR experiences: activity book, diary and art practices for designers to explore and solicit care in Cultural Heritage domain* (Version 2).

⁸ National Research Council, Foundation for Research and Technology Hellas (2023) *D2.2 Stakeholders needs and Requirement Analysis* (Version 2).

3. The ECHOES consultation

3.1 Overall approach

The ECHOES consultation pursues three main objectives. The first is to identify and map the very diverse – and sometimes fragmented – communities working on or with cultural heritage, as they constitute the future users of the Cloud.

The second objective is to collect and analyse the digital practices and needs of these communities, as well as their level of digital literacy. For instance, the consultation seeks to identify possible correlations between professional sectors or occupations and levels of digital literacy. Such insights are intended to inform the design of the Cloud's tools and services, as well as the training and capacity building material that will accompany them.

The third aim consists of capturing the expectations of future users regarding the Cloud. In this sense, the consultation also serves as a means of engagement, encouraging potential users to express their needs and articulate how the Cloud support their work.

To achieve these three aims, the consultation was organised in two steps. The first one consisted of a comprehensive questionnaire. It was then complemented by workshops and focus groups. These complementary activities were organised based on the outcomes of the questionnaire, by identifying under-represented CH communities – areas of professional expertise, occupation or region. They therefore aim to go deeper into the feedback of some communities.

The consultation also contributes to the collaborative dimension of the Cloud. For this reason, several workshops and focus groups were organised in cooperation with WP3, notably within the framework of the collaborative research scenarios series.

Finally, the consultation was conceived as an integral part of ongoing project processes. It provides early insights into the digital needs of CH communities, forming an initial set of requirements for the design of the Cloud's infrastructure, tools and services. These requirements constitute a foundation that will be progressively refined and expanded through iterative development. That is why the consultation was designed through close collaboration with other project work packages that were expected to benefit from its results, particularly during the questionnaire design and testing phases.

3.2 Questionnaire design and methodology

3.2.1 Survey development

The ECHOES questionnaire was developed in continuity with, and inspired by, several existing initiatives (see Section 2). Its objective was to build upon previous work while ensuring coherence with pre-existing approaches. In particular, the ESPADON questionnaire served as the primary model. This comprehensive survey, designed to map

French CH communities and identify their digital needs, significantly informed both the structure and development of the ECHOES questionnaire.

In addition, the questionnaire design drew upon mapping methodologies developed by ECHOES partners, as well as initiatives and infrastructures such as E-RIHS ERIC, ARIADNE RI, CLARIN ERIC, the ATRIUM, CHARTER and PERCEIVE projects.

To ensure that the questionnaire results would be relevant and useful throughout the entire project, the design team also consulted the technical work packages. They provided guidance on the types of data and outcomes needed to support the development of the Cloud's infrastructure, tools, and services.

Structurally, the questionnaire is divided into seven sections:

- Sections A and B focus on identifying the diverse communities engaged in CH.
- Sections C and D examine how these communities use digital datasets, tools, and services in their daily work, as well as the challenges they encounter.
- Sections E and F explore community needs and expectations regarding the Cloud, including requirements for digital tools, services, workflows, and datasets, as well as support for modernising professional practices within collaborative digital environments.
- Section G gathered respondents' interest in the project and asked whether they wished to be contacted for future ECHOES activities.

Before its official launch, the questionnaire underwent a testing phase. Partners involved in Task 4.1 were invited to nominate testers from their networks with diverse expertise to provide feedback on the questionnaire's structure, clarity, and completeness. Feedback was collected from 20 testers. Most of them completed the questionnaire in full while timing themselves, allowing them to comment on its length and manageability. Several also provided detailed suggestions on the questions. Tester nominations were collected at the end of 2024, and feedback was received by the end of January 2025. The design team subsequently incorporated this input, and the questionnaire was officially launched at the end of February 2025.

During the questionnaire design process, the question of vocabulary arose regarding some terms used in the formulation of the questions. To support clear internal communication and effective engagement with the target communities, the ECHOES project glossary was created as a shared vocabulary and published on the [SKOSMOS](#) platform hosted by CNR-ILC, one of the consortium partners.

The glossary initially aggregated the 70 most used terms on the project website, related documentation and the first course developed for the ECHOES Curriculum. The terms have been defined, validated and translated into Italian by members of WP4. The glossary is not exhaustive and does not replace the Digital Twin Heritage Ontology: it is meant as a living resource that supports documentation, data practices, and communication materials, and it is informed by community engagement. A multilingual

version is planned, and the approach is scalable to meet the needs of the ECHOES sister projects. The methodology and contributions workflow are described in more detail in D4.2.⁹

3.2.2 Survey administration

The ECHOES questionnaire was created on LimeSurvey, a free and open-source tool available through RENATER, the French national research and education network. RENATER provides reliable and secure services tailored to the scientific and academic community, ensuring compliance with the European General Data Protection Regulation. The data is hosted in French and European servers, and the information collected in LimeSurvey is specifically hosted on the university server, which offers a trusted option for administering the questionnaire. Given that the connection to this tool is via a university account, the University of Tours domain was used to access it.

The survey was set up based on a validated version shared on the ECHOES Teams group. It included a variety of response formats, including scales, multiple choices, and open-ended questions to capture both quantitative and qualitative data. Terms from the ECHOES glossary were presented in certain questions with their definition thanks to a tooltip, ensuring clarity and minimising potential misinterpretation.

Before answering, the respondents were provided with a brief overview of the ECHOES project and the aim of the consultation. To proceed, they were requested to consent to the use of their data and were informed that it would be processed in accordance with ECHOES' privacy policy and the European General Data Protection Regulation.

Access to the results of the questionnaire directly on LimeSurvey was only available to a restricted number of ECHOES members, including WP4 leader and task leaders.

All the results were regularly uploaded to an Excel master table, which was used to create the Dashboard. This Excel, accessible to the project, did not include the columns containing the emails of respondents. A copy was created in a separate folder and protected by a password. It is only accessible to the WP leader and T4.1 leader.¹⁰

To inform the rest of the consortia and work together on a continued strategy to target misrepresented communities during the time that the survey was open - and before the creation of the Dashboard - charts automatically generated on Limesurvey were used to visualise data from quantitative questions.

The ECHOES questionnaire was launched in February 2025 and remained open until 30 June 2025, following an extension of the original deadline.

⁹ Bakirtzis, N., *et al.* (2026) *Strategy for community building (D4.2)*.

¹⁰ When needed for the complementary consultation activities, specific email addresses of respondents that agreed to be recontacted for further activities, were extracted from the restricted Excel.

3.2.3 Sampling and participation

The ECHOES consultation questionnaire attracted significant engagement from the cultural heritage communities. A total of over 2,065 individuals interacted with the survey, with 464 institutional answers, indicating a strong level of interest in the initiative. Among these:

- 1,303 responses were considered exploitable for the mapping of communities,
- 825 responses were exploitable for the analysis of digital practices and needs,
- 806 responses were fully completed.

This differentiation reflects varying levels of engagement among respondents, with a substantial subset providing complete datasets while a broader group contributed partially to specific sections of the questionnaire.

Figure 4: Overview of the responses to the ECHOES consultation survey

The consultation achieved a broad international reach, with respondents representing 65 countries worldwide, including 31 European countries.

While Europe constitutes the primary geographical focus of the dataset, the responses also demonstrate participation from professionals based in other regions, notably Asia, Africa, and the Americas.

Within Europe, the geographical distribution is uneven, with very strong representation in France, Portugal and Italy followed by other European countries with low participation of Eastern and Northern countries or UK for instance. This disparity should be considered when analysing the representativeness of the dataset.

Figure 5: Geographical coverage

The respondent pool is characterised by a predominance of mid-career professionals with a high level of education, typically holding master's or PhD degrees.

A large proportion of respondents are affiliated with public and non-profit organisations, broadly reflecting the institutional landscape of the cultural heritage sector. The data also show a diverse representation from a variety of organisational types, with academia and research institutions leading, followed by libraries, archives, museums (LAMs), and other heritage-related entities such as governmental agencies and historical monuments and sites.

In terms of professional fields, the consultation captures a wide spectrum of expertise, with a particularly strong presence of professionals and researchers working in heritage conservation and preservation, followed by researchers in social sciences and humanities and those active in education, mediation and audience engagement.

However, professionals active in museology and collection management did not engage with the questionnaire as much as expected, having a lower representation than those active in digital technologies and data management or from archives and documentation fields.

Further details of the respondents' profiles and field of expertise, including quantitative indicators, are included in Section 3.3.2.

Despite the broad participation achieved, some limitations and potential biases should be acknowledged, and are further described in Section 4.4. These factors should be considered when interpreting the results and assessing their generalisability.

3.3 Data analysis and exploitation

3.3.1 The visual dashboard

To facilitate the quantitative analysis of the survey results and to support the qualitative interpretation of the findings, an [interactive dashboard](#) has been developed and is available online.

The dashboard was designed to support the exploration of the raw survey data and to facilitate subsequent analysis of the results. It was released in March 2026, before the 2nd ECHOES Annual Event, so that interested stakeholders could preview the results and use it as a complement to the factsheet. Since the dashboard is intended only to display the raw results of the online questionnaire, it does not analyse associations or correlations between variables and does not attempt to generate data-driven insights.

Structure

The dashboard application is organised into three main components: filters, tabs and subtabs, and plots (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Interactive dashboard application, showing the filter panel, the main tabs and subtabs, and the plot displayed for the selected subtab, illustrating the types of heritage assets with which respondents work

Filters allow users to refine the displayed results according to selected criteria corresponding to questionnaire variables (Figure 6). When a filter is modified, all plots displayed in the dashboard are automatically updated to reflect the new selection.

Tabs and subtabs mirror the structure of the questionnaire. Tabs correspond to the main sections of the questionnaire (Part A, Part B, etc.), while subtabs correspond to individual questions within each section. For example, to explore the results for “C4. Access

Models”, users first select the tab “Part C. Digital Practices and Needs” and then choose the subtab “C4. Access Models”.

Plots are displayed within each subtab and present the responses associated with the selected question. These plots are dynamically updated whenever filters are modified.

The screenshot displays the ECHOES Consultation - Raw Results Dashboard. At the top, there is a 'Filters in use' section with a 'Filters (click to expand/collapse)' header. Below this, there are four dropdown menus for 'Questionnaire: Completed', 'Part A: Education (A1.3)', 'Part A: Institution type (A5)', and 'Part E: Development involvement (E1)'. The 'Part A: Education (A1.3)' dropdown is open, showing options for 'High school diploma', 'Masters', and 'Other'. A 'Close filters menu' button is visible. Below the filters, there are sections for 'GENERAL', 'PART A', 'PART B', 'PART C', 'PART D', 'PART E', and 'PART F', each containing checkboxes for various filter categories. A 'Total respondents matching filters' section at the bottom shows 325 respondents. A 'Reset filters' button is located in the bottom right corner.

Figure 7: Screenshot showing the filters available on the dashboard

For each selected filter, a dropdown menu (in the top part) enables users to restrict the results to respondents matching the desired criteria. Users can add/remove filters using checkboxes (in the bottom part).

Filters

For each filter, users can select one or more values to include in the results (Figure 7). Only responses matching the selected criteria will be displayed. For example, if a user selects “Bachelor’s” and “Master’s” under the filter “Level of Education”, only respondents with one of these education levels will be included in the displayed results. This feature allows users to easily compare response distributions across arbitrary respondent profiles (Figure 7).

Example filters

- Completed: Responses are categorised as *Exploitable*, referring to respondents who completed at least the first two parts of the questionnaire, and *Complete*, referring to respondents who completed all sections of the questionnaire.
- Role: Respondents could complete the questionnaire either as representatives of an institution or in a personal capacity. Depending on the selected role, personal demographic questions such as gender, age, or education level were enabled or disabled.

Tabs, subtabs, and questions included

Tabs and subtabs allow users to navigate through the different questions included in the survey. The dashboard displays only closed questions. Open-ended questions are analysed and discussed in Section 3.3.2. However, the dashboard includes a summary visualisation derived from two key open-ended questions: C2 (What difficulties, if any, do you encounter when using digital tools and resources for your work?) and C3 (In what ways could these tools and services be improved?). The responses to these questions were analysed and tagged according to a set of 20 thematic issues. The identified topics for C2 and C3 questions can be found in Annex 1.

Figure 8: Distribution of responses on the use of objects in respondents' work

Filters allow users to compare response distributions across different respondent profiles. In this example, the distribution of responses on the use of objects in respondents' work is shown for the full sample (top) and for respondents who selected "digital technologies and data management" among their professional activities (bottom).

For communication purposes, a small number of questions were slightly adapted in the dashboard visualisation. For example, question A1.5 asked either "Where are you based?" (for respondents answering in a personal capacity) or "Where is your institution based?" (for institutional representatives). In the dashboard, responses to both questions are consolidated into a single visualisation, which can be displayed either as a bar chart or as a choropleth world map showing participation levels by country.

Similarly, question B1 ("What types of heritage do you work with in your professional activity?") originally included a very detailed set of resource categories and subcategories. In the dashboard, a simplified bar chart is used that displays only the main resource categories.

Plot selection

Since the dashboard is not intended to show correlations between variables, plots are designed to present one question at a time.

All survey questions were categorical. For multiple-choice questions, such as B2 (Assets used), horizontal bar charts were selected because they allow long category labels to be displayed clearly. The same chart type is also used for single-choice questions. In cases with a small number of options, horizontal bar charts are complemented with doughnut charts to provide an alternative visual summary.

GDPR Compliance

Although the dashboard does not include any direct personal identifiers, additional safeguards have been implemented to protect respondents' privacy. First, k-anonymity has been applied so that results are not displayed when a combination of filters yields fewer than ten respondents. Second, certain sensitive filters, including gender, age interval, and country, have been removed from the public version of the dashboard.

Other graphical interface elements

Tooltips are incorporated into both filters and plot titles. These tooltips (Figure 9) provide additional contextual information about the corresponding survey question, for example, whether the question allowed a single response or multiple responses, or whether it was conditional on answers to previous questions.

Figure 9: Example of a questionnaire item tooltip

The tooltip provides contextual guidance for interpreting responses correctly, including whether the question was optional and how many answers could be selected.

3.3.2 Quantitative analysis

This section presents a descriptive overview of the quantitative results collected through the ECHOES Consultation questionnaire. The analysis focuses on key variables related to respondent profiles, heritage domains and practices, digital practices, data sharing and management, and technical infrastructure.

The results are based on the subset of exploitable responses, which vary depending on the section of the questionnaire, and are presented through aggregated figures and distributions.

It has to be noted that the survey allowed respondents to deliver multiple answers in most questions, so each question score must be understood as the sum of times it was selected by all respondents. Although this brings extra complexity in the analysis, it also allows for a richer insight into the topics and conveys the multidisciplinary nature of the heritage sector and its digital dimension.

The following subsections are structured according to the main thematic areas of the questionnaire, providing a consistent overview of the data collected across different dimensions of the cultural heritage community.

Identified communities and fields of expertise

As outlined in section 3.2.3 on sampling and participation, the opening section of the survey was designed to capture the profiles of respondents and their areas of professional expertise. The following section presents a selection of quantitative data derived directly from these responses, providing an overview of the composition of the sample.

The consultation gathered responses from both individual professionals and institutional representatives, with individual respondents accounting for 68.3% of the total.

The majority of respondents are employed (79.3%), followed by self-employed or freelance professionals (10.7%) and entrepreneurs (8.4%).

In terms of organisational affiliation, 49.0% of respondents work in universities, research institutes or research infrastructures, followed by 28.3% working in LAMs and 18.5% working in governmental agencies or other public authorities (question A5). Only 12.0% are based in private for-profit organisations, indicating a stronger representation of the public and non-profit sector (question A4) (see figure 13).

The professional landscape covered by the survey is diverse, encompassing a wide range of activities. A particularly high number of responses were recorded in the area of heritage conservation and preservation (663 responses), followed by research studies in SSH (408), education, mediation and audience engagement (379), digital technologies and data management (346) and documentation, archive and data management (342).

Figure 10: Respondents' institution type

Heritage assets and resources

The results show that respondents engage with a broad spectrum of heritage assets. Tangible heritage is the most frequently reported category, including visual resources (992 responses), textual resources (899) and physical artefacts such as historical and archaeological sites, decorative art, sculpture, textile and other type of movable heritage (828). Intangible and community heritage are also well represented (545 responses), although less frequently (see Figure 11).

A significant proportion of respondents indicated working across multiple types of heritage, reflecting the presence of hybrid and cross-domain professional practices.

In terms of resources studied, physical objects remain central (45.1%), while digital representations, such as 3D surveys, photogrammetry, GIS, and CAD data, are also extensively used (32.5%).

Geographically, the heritage assets addressed are primarily European (91.9%), although respondents also reported working with materials from other regions.

Figure 11: Types of heritage respondents work with

Digital practices and tools

The consultation provides insights into the digital tools and technologies currently used or sought by respondents.

Among data annotation and analysis tools, manual annotation tools for digital assets show the highest levels of engagement (458 responses, 56.6%). Among knowledge representation tools, there is a strong interest in knowledge graphs, semantic web technologies and linked data (331 responses, 54.7%). Within data management tools, data collection management and structuring emerge as the most requested (420 responses, 47.8%). In the area of 3D modelling and visualisation tools, 3D technologies, including scanning, modelling and reconstruction, are the most in demand (517 responses, 32.8%), with strong interest also reported for GIS and virtual reality tools (336 responses, 21.3%, and 303 responses, 19.3%, respectively) (see Figure 15).

Text-based automation tools, such as OCR/HTR and natural language processing, show moderate uptake (138 responses, 17.1%). Visual recognition tools are less widely used (77 responses, 9.5%) but remain of interest to respondents.

Regarding access models, free and open-access services are the most commonly used (30.7%), followed by open-source tools (18.0%), while paid and custom-built solutions are less prevalent (11.2% paid subscription-based services, 9.9% in-house or custom-built tools, 9.6% paid license-based services).

Figure 12: Digital practices and most requested tools

Data creation, management and sharing

The results highlight a range of practices related to data creation, management and sharing.

In terms of data production practices, the answers indicate a predominance of archival research (610 responses), followed by digitisation, transcription and 3D or spatial documentation (456), as well as fieldwork (447) (see Figure 13).

With regard to the objectives of data production, the most common aims are answering research questions (620 responses) and archiving or preserving information (541).

Figure 13: Data production practices

A significant proportion of respondents report not using a Data Management Plan (42.0%), while an equal share (41.2%) indicate that they are not aware of whether such a plan exists within their organisation (see figure 14).

In terms of formats, open data formats are widely used, often in combination with proprietary formats (37.8% open only + 43.6% in combination with closed formats).

Data documentation practices are predominantly based on simple notes (22.3%) and manual descriptions (18.9%), with more formal approaches, such as the use of established standards and protocols (8.1%), being less frequent.

For data storage, local storage solutions are the most common (592 responses indicating the use of local storage solutions for all or at least a large part of data created).

Data sharing practices vary, with respondents indicating that data are shared:

- for specific purposes (332 responses),
- openly without restriction (284 responses),
- upon request (232 responses),
- under a specific license (231 responses).

The main challenges associated with data sharing include data quality (13.4%), data security (12.7%), risk of misuse (12.6%), effort and resource requirements (12.4%) and legal and regulatory constraints (12.3%).

Figure 14: Data management practices

Systems, infrastructure and development

A notable number of respondents (187) report involvement in system and infrastructure management, indicating the presence of technical expertise within the community. The most commonly used database types are relational (46.9%) and object-oriented (33.2%) databases.

Servers are widely used to support:

- data storage (120 responses),
- databases (119 responses),
- web and applications (102 responses).

Backup and redundancy practices are also commonly implemented (110 responses).

Respondents contribute to the development of digital tools in various roles, most frequently as:

- project coordinators (25.6%),
- concept designers (25.6%),
- end-users or testers (25.5%).

Collaboration with development teams typically takes place through formal or semi-formal mechanisms, such as regular meetings and feedback sessions (30.2%), or through direct involvement in iterative development and testing cycles (21.2%). Email-based communication (14.2%) is also reported.

3.3.3 Qualitative analysis

Across the different questionnaire sections, there were open-ended questions able to supplement the survey analysis with qualitative evidence, useful to map and understand the Cloud communities, their needs and expectations. These ranged from fully open answers to just an open text option as “other” in multiple-choice questions.

All these open-ended questions require tailored approaches as some are fundamental for the global, comprehensive and integrated analysis of results, while others deliver specific information useful to enrich our collection of references and resources (controlled vocabularies, tools developed by respondents, etc).

All open answers from all responses were used, including the non-completed ones, for a total of 1303 responses. Within this universe of open answers, deeper analysis was carried out in the following ones, clustered by the approach taken:

- The “Other” option in closed questions.
- Needs and expectations (C2 and C3).
- Occupation (A3).

The “Other” option in closed questions

The “Other” option in closed questions was present in: B1, C4, D1, D2, D3, D4, D8.1, D13, D14, E3, E4, E6, F2, F2.2, F3, F4, F7, F8. It is important to highlight that all these options were not extensively/widely used by respondents. The question B1 “Which types of heritage assets do you work with?” had 60 answers detailing asset typologies or specific features. As for the remaining ones, the responses ranged from 27 respondents in D3 to 1 respondent in E3 and A1.3. Nonetheless, these answers were used to:

- Provide extra detail or specificity to answering “yes” (as evident in B1).
- Express doubts regarding the question itself, stating comments as the term 'data' is too vague” or “Hmm not sure”.
- Express “n/a” or “none” statement in questions where “no” was not an option.
- Illustrate terminology and conceptual misunderstandings from the respondents regarding what is being asked, e.g. respondents confused data type (historical records, surveys, interviews, experimental results) with data format (3D, videos, print).
- In very few cases, refer to a subcategory the respondent understood to be absent.

These answers reinforced the quantitative analysis on the closed answers and were useful as evidence to support the perception of respondents’ digital practices.

Needs and expectations (C2 and C3)

Section C is the first section of the survey enquiring about digital practices, levels of digital literacy and the challenges respondents find when working in the digital environment. Within this scope, C2 and C3 captured respondents’ needs and expectations towards the Cloud. The C2. *“What difficulties, if any, do you encounter when using digital tools and resources for your work? How do these affect your ability to achieve your goals?”* already proposed suggestions of possible difficulties and impacts using

digital services and tools. Question C3. *“In what ways could these tools and services be improved? Are there any specific functionalities or improvements you would find helpful?”* enquired on suggestions for improvements that would support the development of the Cloud.

The analysis of both questions required an automated AI-assisted approach applied to the respondent’s answers as they were descriptive, complex, and addressed several topics in each answer. The process started with the analysis of C2, and the model went through several development iterations to address issues such as failing to identify all topics mentioned in each answer and to establish a robust strategy for assessing potential model hallucinations.

Ultimately, the prompts were designed to:

- Identify the main topics (e.g., lack of interoperability, multilingualism issues) across all responses and present the results clustered by topic.
- Extract the specific utterances in each response corresponding to each topic (including the row reference in the Excel file and the literal excerpt from the answer).

This output enabled us to: (a) develop a script to automatically verify that the corresponding Excel cell contained the correct literal excerpt from the response, and (b) generate a restructured Excel file with rearranged columns to facilitate human validation of the model’s predictions. This validation was conducted on a sample of responses to estimate the model’s *precision* (i.e., the proportion of predicted positives that were correct) and *recall* (i.e., the proportion of actual positives that were correctly identified).

As part of the model’s development and refinement process, its outputs were manually verified and validated. To assess the reliability of the results, five topic clusters were selected, including both those with more than 100 associated responses and smaller topic clusters, which were considered more prone to lower confidence. In addition, when evaluating the presence of a given topic within a response, we cross-checked whether other relevant topics in the same response had also been correctly identified and assigned to their respective clusters. Based on a sample of 133 responses, the model achieved an estimated precision above 98% and a recall of approximately 90%.

These results demonstrated the high level of confidence of the model to analyse, identify, and cluster respondents’ answers. In the end, C2 answers were aggregated into 20 clusters, ranging from high occurrences to lower.

The improved model from the analysis of C2 was then applied to the C3 responses. These were also aggregated into 20 clusters, mirroring the previously identified typologies of difficulties, but with a stronger focus on the operationalisation and detailing of the solutions.

The resulting clusters provide a comprehensive overview of the main concerns and difficulties faced by professionals when working in digital environments. They cover a wide range of topics, from data-related issues and system interoperability to digital literacy. The clusters were ranked according to their frequency, from highest to lowest occurrence (see Annex 1 - C2 and C3 Clusters list).

Notwithstanding, these answers are framed by respondents' professional affiliation, being mainly from public and non-profit organisations such as Universities and research centres or heritage institutions representing the GLAM sector. Although very representative of the variety of the heritage professional landscape, the consultation nevertheless carries some bias in representing the whole EU heritage universe. A good example is the language barrier, having such a low score. The survey circulated only in English, and this is an impediment for non-English fluent speakers to fully comprehend the questions and answer the complexity of the topics covered.

Another impression derives from the analysis of the high-rated challenges and difficulties, such as licensing cost, steep learning curves and compatibility and interoperability. Respondents mentioned that the investment in efforts and resources (financial, human, time) put into learning and using digital services and tools is of low added value in terms of productivity and efficiency in organisations, businesses and professionals' practice. This issue was not identified as a topic per se, but it is expressed indirectly by statements such as: "a great waste of time in handling digital technologies, instead of dedicating ourselves to studying research themes and problems", "time for which is rarely budgeted, and my employer has little flexibility in this regard." or "technology, files, programs become obsolete before they become cost effective" and "require significant time to learn, impacting productivity".

However, some of these needs are out of the scope of ECHOES, while others can be directly resolved or addressed within ECHOES mandate. A case in point is the internet connectivity and dependency; although improving the internet services of institutions is out of scope, ECHOES can promote and nurture the development of offline services and tools. ECHOES can also advocate for sustainable policies and infrastructures in heritage digital practices or tailored funding for smaller institutions. It cannot resolve systemic insufficiency of digital storage, but can provide storage capacity for collaboration opportunities. Overall, many of the improvements suggested by respondents are already embedded in the Cloud architecture design, its services and tools. Expectations regarding data quality and security, standards and controlled vocabularies, intuitive interfaces and easy-to-use tools for professionals, to name just a few, are key features of the Cloud. Further details on the analysis of the needs and expectations of the communities engaged in the ECHOES consultation are provided in Section 5.

Occupation (A3)

In Section A of the survey, question A3. *What is your current occupation? Please specify your role(s), your field of study (if you're a student), and/or your job title (if you're employed)* was answered by the majority of respondents in the exploitable answers and is of key importance to pinpoint the role of each respondent in the heritage sector. However, being an open-ended answer, responses were considerably diverse, displaying answers with a single professional title to others describing the full training background or the career paths of a respondent. A dual approach made of automated and manual curation was developed, aiming to deliver a manageable and reasonable list of occupations.

Existing official taxonomies for occupations at the European level present a partial image of those active in the heritage sector. This reality has been addressed by several EU projects and initiatives; however, mismatches are not yet fully resolved for the heritage sector.

To overcome this shortcoming, and as a starting point for the harmonisation and cleaning of A3 answers, the results of the CHARTER survey were used. The project delivered a list of occupations that grasped a wider variety of information closer to reality, overcoming many of the outdated entries of official taxonomies. Even so, the survey was designed using key EU taxonomies: ISCO-08 (international framework last updated in 2008); ESCO (European framework for occupations and skills, derived from ISCO, adding extra information from ongoing non-systematic efforts from Member States); and each responding country's national occupational framework (NOC). The survey was focused on heritage practice and not aimed at technological and computer sciences, unlike ECHOES; hence, its results were less expressive in describing these professions.

An automated approach was taken and tested to match ECHOES respondents with CHARTER survey occupations, resulting in a list of harmonised and normalised occupations, which was then manually revised, taking into consideration other ECHOES questions (A2 on working status; A5 with the type of organisation respondents work for; and A6 with fields of practice) to better identify the occupation being put forward by respondents.

It is essential to note some aspects of this curation process that may impact the interpretation of the results. The heritage sector is highly transdisciplinary and is grounded in national and regional cultural dimensions. These features produce complex technical and scientific contexts, varied languages with diverse cultural and semantic meanings that are often difficult to harmonise and translate adequately into English. This is obvious in how people describe their jobs and how professional profile titles are defined and conferred.

It was developed an interactive tool to analyse and visualise the survey results for different occupation categories and is presented in Section 4.2.3.

3.4 Complementary consultation activities and feedback opportunities

3.4.1 Overview and methodology

To ensure the robustness, interpretability, and practical relevance of the findings derived from the ECHOES consultation survey, a set of complementary activities was implemented to verify and further substantiate the survey results. While the survey provides a comprehensive overview of community profiles, needs, and expectations, its findings may be influenced by the subjectivity of responses and the composition of the sample.

These complementary activities were designed to:

- Provide an opportunity for collective reflection on survey results.
- Verify the accuracy and clarity of their interpretation.
- Assess the representativeness of identified community clusters and personas.
- Reach underrepresented or highly specialised stakeholder groups.
- Cross-check reported needs against real-world practices and workflows.
- Refine and prioritise requirements to inform other Work Packages.

To achieve these objectives, ECHOES adopted a triangulation approach, combining quantitative survey data with qualitative feedback and practice-based evidence gathered through targeted engagement activities. This approach enabled a more grounded and participatory understanding of community needs, supporting the refinement of community clusters and strengthening engagement with underrepresented groups.

The validation framework was conceived as a multi-stage, iterative process integrating complementary methods and stakeholder perspectives.

The methodology consists of the organisation of workshops, focus groups, and targeted consultations that combine the presentation of survey findings with interactive discussion (for further details on these activities, see the following Section). This approach allows a transition from broad survey input to more focused and in-depth consultation.

Despite efforts to ensure inclusivity and robustness, some limitations remain, including imbalances in participation across regions and sectors, and still low number of events targeting more in-depth enquiry to specific professional groups or heritage domains. These will be addressed through continued engagement and iterative validation in subsequent project phases.

The integration of these complementary activities has strengthened the reliability and practical relevance of the consultation results, ensuring that the project's outcomes are firmly grounded in the needs and realities of the communities involved.

3.4.2 Workshops & focus groups

A series of activities was implemented to complement the consultation survey by enabling more targeted, interactive, and qualitative engagement with stakeholders across different domains, professional profiles, and geographic areas. They were organised in different formats (see Table below):

- **Interactive workshops** were used to present key survey results and engage participants in structured discussions, allowing for the collective prioritisation of needs and the refinement of emerging interpretations.
- **Domain-specific focus groups** (e.g. built heritage, conservation-restoration, museum curation, networks) provided detailed qualitative insights into sectoral practices, challenges, and expectations, contributing to a more contextualised understanding of the survey outcomes.

Additional consultation activities included bilateral meetings with project partners, aimed to engage communities that appear underrepresented in the survey sample, particularly from a geographical perspective.

Further sessions are planned in the coming months to expand coverage across regions, domains, and areas of expertise, with the aim of capturing a broader range of perspectives and strengthening the inclusiveness of the consultation process.

Table 1: Overview of workshops and focus groups

Event	Date	Location	Type	Participants (n)	Profile	Scope
Brussels Policy Event	12/2024	Brussels	Workshop	80 + 600 online	Policy, RI, CH institutions	European
CAA Workshop	05/2025	Athens	Workshop	~150	Researchers, IT, archaeologists	International
DARIAH Event	06/2025	Göttingen	Workshop series	~250	Researchers, RI	European
Digital Heritage	09/2025	Siena	Workshop	~80	Mixed CH community	International
ASKI focus group	10/2025	Athens	Focus group	~10	Historians, archivists	National
Nicosia workshop	11/2025	Nicosia	Workshop	~15-20	CH professionals (museum)	National
Marseille workshop	12/2025	Marseille	Workshop	~10	Conservators, scientists	Regional
German-speaking webinar	01/2026	Online	Workshop	~60	Mixed CH community	Regional
Intangible FG	01/2026	Online	Focus group	~20	Linguists, archivists	International
Built heritage FG	02/2026	Online	Focus group	~25	Built heritage experts	International
INP focus groups	03/2026	Paris	Focus groups	~30	Conservator-restorers, curators, art historians	European
Networks FG	04/2026	Online	Focus group	14	Networks, umbrella organisations	European

Workshops

Brussels high-level policy event and workshop – Brussels, 12 December 2024

Type of activity

Workshop and policy event

Context and objectives

This high-level event aimed to position ECHOES within the European cultural heritage and research policy landscape, while collecting initial feedback on community needs and expectations and fostering dialogue with key institutional stakeholders.

Participants

- Number of participants: ~80 in person; ~600 online
- Profile: representatives of research funding bodies, policy makers, research infrastructures, cultural heritage institutions, and technical service providers

Format and methodology

The event combined project presentations with interactive engagement tools (e.g. Wooclap), enabling real-time feedback collection and audience participation.

Key takeaways

- Strong interest in coordination between research infrastructures, funding bodies and cultural heritage institutions
- Need for alignment between policy frameworks and technical development of the Cloud
- Importance of interoperability and cross-domain collaboration at the European level

CAA Conference workshop – Athens, 5-9 May 2025

Type of activity

Conference workshop

Context and objectives

Organised within the CAA conference, this workshop aimed to engage a technically advanced research community and to test consultation and engagement approaches with digitally mature stakeholders.

Participants

- Number of participants: ~150
- Profile: archaeologists, researchers, IT specialists, digital heritage professionals
- Scope: international

Format and methodology

The session combined presentations and interactive exercises, enabling structured feedback collection on tools, practices and expectations.

Key takeaways

- Strong reliance on advanced digital tools (GIS, 3D modelling, AI, programming environments)
- Growing importance of AI and computational methods in heritage research workflows
- Limited use of collaborative platforms, highlighting gaps in current infrastructures
- Strong demand for integrated environments supporting data access, organisation and reuse

Further details can be found in Annex 2.

DARIAH Annual Event – Göttingen, 17-20 June 2025

Type of activity

Workshop series and engagement activities

Context and objectives

ECHOES participated in the DARIAH Annual Event to engage with research infrastructures and academic communities, and to test co-design approaches and consultation strategies.

Participants

- Number of participants: ~250
- Profile: researchers, infrastructure providers, cultural heritage experts
- Scope: European

Format and methodology

Activities included a co-design workshop on user and research collaboration scenarios, a “Consultation Corner” enabling one-to-one exchanges, and participation in panel discussions.

Key takeaways

- Strong interest in collaborative research scenarios and cross-infrastructure workflows
- Need to better integrate tools and services within existing research practices
- Value of direct interaction formats for collecting targeted and actionable feedback

Digital heritage conference workshop – Siena, 8-12 September 2025

Type of activity

Conference workshop

Context and objectives

This workshop aimed to engage a broad and interdisciplinary audience and to collect feedback on consultation themes and preliminary findings.

Participants

- Number of participants: ~80
- Profile: researchers, cultural heritage professionals, digital experts, policy makers, curators
- Scope: international

Format and methodology

The session combined presentations, roundtables and interactive discussions structured around consultation topics.

Key takeaways

- Need for cross-domain integration of tools, data and services
- Importance of supporting diverse and interdisciplinary workflows
- Strong interest in shared infrastructures enabling collaboration across sectors

Collaborative research scenarios workshop – Nicosia, 21 November 2025

Type of activity

Workshop / focus group

Context and objectives

This joint WP3–WP4–WP7 activity focused on collaborative research scenarios, exploring cross-institutional and professional (?) workflows and the role of the Cultural Heritage Cloud.

Participants

- Number of participants: ~15-20
- Profile: cultural heritage professionals and researchers
- Scope: national/regional

Format and methodology

Participants engaged in structured discussions and scenario-based exercises to analyse workflows and identify collaboration needs.

Key takeaways

- Need for infrastructures supporting collaborative and distributed research
- Importance of aligning digital tools with real-world workflows

- Demand for flexible solutions supporting cross-institutional cooperation and smooth professional collaboration

Collaborative research scenarios workshop – Marseille, 9–10 December 2025

Type of activity

Workshop

Context and objectives

This workshop aimed to explore real-world professional practices and identify how the Cultural Heritage Cloud could support interdisciplinary workflows.

Participants

- Number of participants: ~10
- Profile: conservator-restorers, conservation scientists, documentation specialists, digital experts
- Scope: regional

Format and methodology

Participants worked collaboratively around a specific heritage object, analysing workflows and identifying where digital tools and services could provide support.

Key takeaways

- Importance of integrating digital tools within existing conservation and documentation workflows
- Need to support interdisciplinary collaboration between scientific, technical and heritage professionals
- Relevance of practice-based validation for identifying concrete user needs

German-speaking communities webinar – Online, 14 January 2026

Type of activity

Webinar

Context and objectives

This session aimed to engage German-speaking cultural heritage communities and gather region-specific feedback.

Participants

- Number of participants: ~60
- Profile: cultural heritage professionals and institutions
- Scope: regional (Austria, Germany, Switzerland, Belgium, Netherlands, Italy)

Format and methodology

Online session combining the presentation of ECHOES and its consultation results, two keynotes, a roundtable with the Cultural Heritage Cloud’s sister projects as well as interactive engagement tools (e.g. Wooclap).

Key takeaways

- Importance of language-specific communication and regional engagement
- Need to adapt dissemination strategies to different communities
- Value of regional networking formats in strengthening participation and collaboration

Focus Groups

Interdisciplinary focus group – Athens (ASKI), 21 October 2025

Type of activity

Focus group

Context and objectives

This session aimed to explore interdisciplinary workflows and collaboration practices across different cultural heritage domains within the framework of collaborative research scenarios.

Participants

- Number of participants: ~10
- Profile: historians, archivists, librarians, cultural heritage communication specialists
- Scope: national

Format and methodology

Participants engaged in hands-on discussions to map daily practices, identify collaboration barriers and reflect on potential support from the Cultural Heritage Cloud.

Key takeaways

- Strong need for tools supporting interdisciplinary and cross-institutional collaboration
- Importance of integrating research, documentation, communication and technical workflows
- Diversity of collaboration scenarios, from small-scale research to large international projects
- Need for flexible and scalable infrastructures supporting different collaboration models

Intangible heritage focus group – Online, 19 January 2026

Type of activity

Focus group

Context and objectives

This session focused on the management and use of intangible cultural heritage data, particularly oral archives, addressing technical, legal and ethical challenges.

Participants

- Number of participants: ~20
- Profile: linguists, archivists, researchers, legal and ethical experts
- Scope: international

Format and methodology

The discussion combined thematic inputs and structured exchanges on data practices, governance and constraints.

Key takeaways

- Need for interdisciplinary approaches combining archival science, linguistics and legal expertise
- Importance of clear consent procedures and ethical frameworks for sensitive data
- Relevance of Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIA) for risk mitigation
- Demand for secure and controlled access mechanisms (e.g. federated access, restricted environments)
- Strong emphasis on responsible data handling and long-term accessibility

Built heritage focus group – Online, 26 February 2026

Type of activity

Focus group

Context and objectives

This session explored practices and needs related to built heritage, focusing on documentation, conservation and data integration.

Participants

- Number of participants: ~25
- Profile: built heritage professionals, conservation experts, researchers
- Scope: international

Format and methodology

Participants discussed workflows involving heterogeneous data sources and challenges in data integration and reuse.

Key takeaways

- Need to integrate heterogeneous datasets (2D/3D documentation, geospatial data, condition assessments)
- Importance of interoperability between platforms, standards and tools
- Need for workflows connecting fieldwork, documentation and analysis
- Demand for infrastructures supporting complex, multi-scale datasets and long-term preservation

Profession/occupation-specific focus group – Paris (INP), 31 March 2026

Type of activity

Focus groups

Context and objectives

These sessions aimed to explore profession-specific workflows, practices and expectations in relation to digital infrastructures.

Participants

- Number of participants: ~30
- Profile: curators, art historians, conservator-restorers
- Scope: European

Format and methodology

Full day workshop combining the presentation of ECHOES and its consultation results with parallel group discussions structured by professional profile, focusing on daily practices and workflow, tools, needs and expectations towards the Cloud.

Key takeaways

- Strong diversity of workflows across professional roles, but with high convergence on their digital needs and expectations towards the Cloud
- Data is fragmented across repositories, with no interoperability of systems or tools, a lack of shared standards in terminology and metadata
- Need for tools tailored to domain-specific practices
- Need for metadata common standards, able to convey domain specificities without deterring richness of knowledge or deterring innovation
- All groups struggle with complex access rights, whether due to institutional policies, legal restrictions, or proprietary formats
- Tailored capacity building and ongoing support are essential for professionals and institutions to overcome uneven levels of digital literacy and counteract resistance to change

- Need for long-term data management and sustainable systems, to prevent obsolescence. Importance of aligning digital solutions with professional realities and constraints, using real user cases for validation processes

Further details can be found in Annex 2.

Networks and Umbrella Organisations Focus Group – Online, 8 April 2026

Type of activity

Focus group

Context and objectives

This session focused on the features that would support the adoption of the Cloud by cultural heritage professionals represented by the participating networks. It also addressed the role of networks and umbrella organisations in supporting dissemination, coordination and uptake of the Cultural Heritage Cloud.

Participants

- Number of participants: 14
- Profile: representatives of networks and umbrella organisations present in ECHOES: APEF – Archives Portal Foundation, ARIADNE, E.C.C.O. - European Confederation of Conservators-Restorers, ICOM International - AVICOM, ICOM Portugal, Michael Culture Association, NEMO (Working Group on Digital Transformation).
- Scope: European

Format and methodology

Following introductory presentations on the Cloud and its architecture, participants exchanged through a structured dialogue exchanging views on needs, concerns, and expectations concerning the Cloud and its functioning.

Key takeaways

- Key concerns focused on interoperability, data standardisation, to overcome existing fragmentation with multiple systems and incompatible metadata. Fear that the Cloud adds complexity rather than resolves it. Concerns with data overload without improved usability, stressing that more data is only valuable if it is easier to visualise, analyse and use.
- Trust, data quality, and data validation, accountability, responsibility and control mechanisms are fundamental. It was suggested that existing good practices from social sciences research platforms for publication and peer validation could be of inspiration.
- Long-term storage and data permanence are essential requirements, alongside financial viability (including smaller institutions) and environmental sustainability. Within institutions technical barriers, low digital capacity, lack of training, limited

technical support, and organisational resistance, influence adoption. Concerns about inclusiveness and inequality across territories, professional groups or heritage typologies can reinforce gaps between countries, institution sizes, and levels of digital maturity. Governance models must be inclusive and avoid bias toward already visible actors.

- Additional concerns included platform performance, useful and usable by professionals, and the need to avoid mismatch between the Cloud's model and actual research practices, which are often project-based. It was suggested to link the use of the Cloud as the requirements of COST-ACTION projects in terms of publication of results.

In conclusion, the Cloud is seen as a highly promising but demanding initiative. Its success depends on trust, long-term sustainability of its services and data, robust equalitarian governance, user-centred efficiency and usability. Rather than becoming another standalone platform, it should act as an invisible layer that enhances and simplifies existing practices and platforms.

Further details can be found in Annex 2.

3.4.3 CartoEchoes

CartoEchoes is a web application that uses primarily data obtained from the Mapping of Interest (See section “2.1 Mapping of interest”) to create a semantic cartography. Its primary aim is to demonstrate how Semantic Web data can be created, used, and visualised. To this end, a simple ontology called PAIR (Projects, Actors, Ideas, Resources) is used. PAIR is developed and maintained by the [Virtual Assembly](#), a group of developers who build and maintain interoperable Semantic Web solutions based on W3C standards. Both PAIR and the SemApps and Archipelago solutions are adapted to the ECHOES context.

The resulting frontend presents the actors, projects, and tools involved, along with their relationships. The way Semantic Web data is created, used, and visualised within this framework is illustrated below.

Figure 15: CartoEchoes schema

For now, data has been successfully imported from:

- CSV files generated from the PDF files of the letters of interest
- SPARQL Endpoints (Wikidata, CORDIS)
- SSHOC Marketplace

The CartoEchoes web application will be hosted on a PCSS production server. In the next phase of the project, the ECHOES Questionnaire data will be added to expand this cartography, together with [Cloud tools](#) currently presented in the project's website and future tools from the upcoming sister-projects.

4. Atlas of communities

4.1 Objectives of the Atlas

The Cultural Heritage Cloud aims to deliver a single integrated digital environment that cuts across all heritage domains, siloed fields of expertise, institutional barriers, and linguistic diversity, and brings together professionals to co-create and enhance heritage knowledge.

Similarly, the concept of the Cloud federated community, as proposed by ECHOES, marks a shift away from traditional, discipline-based affiliations toward a more fluid and digital practice-oriented model of collaboration and inclusion. Heritage practitioners are typically grounded in a specific domain, expertise, discipline, institutional or professional affiliation and may operate across varying governance levels. However, upon joining the Cloud, these affiliations are expanded and reframed through shared digital practices, tools, and interactions within the infrastructure. This transformation enables the breaking down of silos across disciplines, professional roles, and institutional frameworks, establishing an additional layer of connection based on common needs, expectations, and modes of engagement with digital environments. In this sense, the Cloud does not replace disciplinary specificity but rather complements it, fostering a transversal federated community constituted of existing communities and networks across the cultural heritage landscape, understood through the lens of their digital practices and literacy.

Within this context, the proposal to design an Atlas of communities for the Cloud becomes a critical and complex exercise. The Atlas should not be understood merely as the map of heritage practice, governance and research made visible in a digital environment, but as a unified scheme that captures both current and future actors engaging with the Cloud. These range from users who access and consult resources to those who actively contribute by enriching the digital heritage assets or by developing and refining services, tools, and workflows, as well as those operating in policy making, and institutional oversight and management, or even those external actors contributing and supporting the development of the Cloud's potential for the creation and enhancement of knowledge.

The key challenge lies in how to conceptualise the Atlas in a way that clusters all these actors, in particular professionals, by shared practices, responsibilities and constraints in their work with cultural heritage data, tools, and services - as well as common needs and expectations toward the Cloud - without disrupting the existing landscape of the heritage sector, the professional roles or institutional mandates within. The Atlas of the Cloud communities is more than a map, is an approach to convey two different realities the heritage practice based and the digital practice led.

The Cloud environment is the connecting dimension where both contact and where solutions are developed and presented to facilitate users' work and progressive uptake of the Cloud.

The ECHOES consultation survey described in Section 3 delivered insights that allow distinct digital behavioural patterns to be structured according to the respondents' professional context and role within the cultural heritage ecosystem - including working status, organisation type, field of activity and types of heritage assets - while simultaneously capturing respondents' engagement with digital tools and data creation, documentation, storage, sharing and reuse, as well as their level of technical collaboration, active responsibility in digital infrastructures, and consequently their perceived challenges and expectations towards the Cloud. This approach enables the identification of recurring cluster profiles by revealing how respondents position themselves within the Cloud's digital environment. Such clusters can be interpreted as personas, offering profiles that are closer to reality and easily relatable for heritage professionals who may recognise themselves in the digital routines of their daily practice. The identification of clusters and personas therefore constitutes an intermediate analytical step that makes it possible to translate the diversity of survey responses into coherent community profiles, which can subsequently be mapped, compared and positioned within the multilayer structure of the Atlas.

In this perspective, the Atlas is conceived as a relational and practice-oriented representation of the cultural heritage ecosystem, combining structural characteristics of the heritage landscape with behavioural and digital dimensions emerging from the consultation activities. It is designed as a multilayer representation of these dimensions, their constituent elements, and the relationships and interdependencies that connect them within the cultural heritage ecosystem.

The following Section 4.2 introduces the cluster profiles and personas derived from the consultation analysis, which constitute the analytical foundation for the development of the Atlas of communities presented in Section 4.3.

4.2 From cluster profiles to persona development

4.2.1 Cluster profiles identification

To interpret the results of the ECHOES consultation beyond aggregated statistics, a community clustering exercise was conducted to identify recurring profiles and professional communities among survey respondents. This step aimed to capture patterns of practice, responsibility and digital engagement that cut across individual responses, providing a structured representation of the diversity of actors interacting with cultural heritage data.

The clustering process was based on responses collected through the ECHOES consultation questionnaire, with a primary focus on Sections A to F. Rather than applying automated statistical clustering techniques, the analysis followed a rule-based and interpretative approach, better suited to the exploratory nature of the consultation and to the need for results that are transparent, explainable and directly usable in subsequent co-design activities.

The identification of user profiles was guided by two complementary dimensions. On the one hand, structural variables were used to describe respondents' professional context and positioning within the cultural heritage ecosystem, including working status, organisation type, field of activity and types of heritage assets. On the other hand, behavioural variables captured how respondents engage with digital tools and data, including practices related to data creation, documentation, storage, sharing and reuse, collaboration with technical actors, responsibility for infrastructures, and perceived barriers.

Rather than relying on single variables, clusters emerged through the identification of recurring combinations of responses across multiple questions. As such, user profiles should be understood as analytical constructs that highlight dominant patterns within the data, rather than rigid or mutually exclusive categories. Overlap between profiles is expected and reflects the hybrid and evolving nature of professional roles in the cultural heritage sector.

This process led to the identification of a diverse set of user profiles, capturing different positions within the ecosystem, including data producers and data managers, technical developers and semantic specialists, cultural communicators, institutional actors, freelance professionals and profiles characterised by varying levels of digital maturity or by a strong focus on data governance and policy.

Figure 16: Cluster profiles identified from the survey responses

The table below provides an overview of the cluster profiles identified through the analysis of the consultation data. It summarises the main characteristics and needs of each profile, offering a synthetic view of the diversity of communities engaged in the cultural heritage ecosystem.

Table 2: Overview of cluster profiles

Cluster profile	Description	Key characteristics	Main needs
Academia and Research	Research-oriented actors combining analysis, interpretation and dissemination of heritage knowledge in academic contexts.	Mixed digital practices, research-driven workflows, hybrid data environments	Interoperability, reusable datasets, metadata support, training
Cultural Communicator	Actors focused on education, mediation and public engagement using heritage content.	Audience-oriented, lightweight tools, content reuse for communication	User-friendly tools, curated data, rights-cleared content
Data Documenters / Managers	Professionals managing documentation, metadata and long-term stewardship of heritage data.	Strong use of standards, structured documentation, governance role	Metadata harmonisation, preservation, governance tools
Data Producers (Scientific)	Technically engaged actors producing and analysing research data across workflows.	Data-intensive workflows, use of advanced tools (3D, GIS), analytical focus	Advanced tools, scalable infrastructure, FAIR support
Emerging Professionals / Early Career	Early-career actors building skills and entering digital heritage environments.	Learning-oriented, partial tool adoption, evolving practices	Training, onboarding, mentoring, guidance
Freelance / Self-Employed	Independent professionals working in project-based and resource-constrained contexts.	Limited infrastructure, flexible workflows, reliance on personal tools	Affordable tools, access to infrastructure, training
Institutional Anchors	Actors embedded in organisations managing collections, data and institutional workflows.	Institutional workflows, reliance on repositories and policies, continuity	Integration, controlled access, storage, governance support
Low-Digital Users	Communities with limited digital maturity and low adoption of structured tools.	Low tool adoption, reliance on local storage, informal practices	Simple tools, basic training, support
Open Data & Policy-Oriented	Actors promoting open data, FAIR principles and governance frameworks.	Focus on FAIR principles, policy alignment, advocacy role	Licensing clarity, FAIR tools, sustainable infrastructures

Professional Heritage Practitioners	Operational professionals working on conservation, documentation and heritage management.	Practice-based workflows, domain-specific methods, compliance needs	Usability, workflow integration, standards, training
Semantic Engineer / Data Architect	Specialists in interoperability, semantic modelling and structured data integration.	Use of ontologies, linked data, structured data integration	Ontology alignment, mapping tools, validation services
Technical Developers	Actors designing and implementing digital tools, platforms and services.	Development-oriented, focus on integration and performance	APIs, reusable data, documentation, interoperability

Beyond the identification of profiles, a more in-depth analysis was carried out for each cluster. This included the systematic exploration of key insights emerging from the survey responses, through the comparison of relevant questions across sections. By analysing how variables relating to data practices, infrastructures, governance, collaboration and perceived barriers interact with each other, it was possible to better understand the digital practices, needs and expectations associated with each profile in relation to the Cultural Heritage Cloud. The results of this comparative analysis, including the mapping between survey questions, response options and cluster definitions, are presented in detail in Annex 3.

4.2.2 Interactive app for profile analysis

To support the exploration and interpretation of the cluster profiles, an [interactive web application](#) has been developed and is available online.

The application was designed to present the analytical profiles in an accessible and comparative format, complementing Annex 3, and facilitating the inspection of profile-specific results. The home page displays the set of profiles, with one card per profile and an indication of the number of respondents included in each group (Figure 17). Users can either open an individual profile or select profiles for comparison.

Figure 17: Main page of the interactive profile analysis application, showing the full set of cluster profiles as cards. Each card displays the profile name, a short description, and the number of respondents in the profile.

For each profile, the application displays the profile description and the results for selected survey questions. Questions are organised into thematic groups, reflecting the main analytical dimensions used in the profile analysis, including socio-professional characteristics, heritage assets, practices and needs, data creation and use, tool development and infrastructure. Individual question results are shown as horizontal bar charts, displaying both the number of respondents and the corresponding proportion for each response option (Figure 18).

Figure 18: Analysis of individual questions for a selected profile

The example shows the Academia and Research profile and the distribution of responses to a question on data production practices.

The application also includes a cross-analysis function for pairs of questions within the same profile. Users can select two questions and inspect the corresponding contingency or co-occurrence table (Figure 19). This feature supports a more detailed interpretation of how selected answers relate to each other within a given profile. For a correct interpretation of the count within each cell, the application clearly indicates if both selected questions are single-choice (showing a contingency table, where the sum of counts for a choice cannot exceed the number of respondents with the selected profile) or if one or both questions are multiple-choice (switching to a co-occurrence table that shows the overlaps between selected choices in the two questions).

Since this analysis requires the display of paired data, additional privacy safeguards have been applied, such as grouping low-frequency categories into an "Other" category and suppressing cells with small counts for GDPR compliance.

Figure 19: Cross-analysis of two questions for the same profile

The example shows a contingency table for the Academia and Research profile, displaying intersections between selected responses to two survey questions.

In the comparison mode, users can select up to five profiles and compare them through radar charts (Figure 20). These visualisations make it possible to compare response patterns across profiles for a selected question, supporting the identification of similarities and differences between profiles. The radar chart can be displayed either using absolute proportions or with a normalised radius, allowing users to focus either on overall response levels or on relative differences between profiles.

Figure 20: Cross-profile comparison using a radar chart

The example compares selected profiles across response options for a question on the types of tools or services respondents were involved in developing.

4.2.3 Interactive app for occupation analysis

Similarly, we created an [interactive web application](#) to support the exploration and interpretation of the different occupations identified from the ECHOES consultation (Section 3.3.3).

The occupations identified were grouped into 12 categories (Annex 4) to increase the number of respondents per category and enable meaningful analyses. Respondents' open answers were curated manually with the support of previous research on professional profiles in heritage, research and digital humanities and occupational framework (ISCO) which were used as proxy to identify similar profiles and harmonise titles. The home page displays the full set of occupation categories, with one card per category and an indication of the number of respondents included (Figure 21).

Figure 21: Main page of the interactive occupation analysis application, showing the set of occupation categories as cards

As in the previous profile analysis application, the application shows the description of the occupation category and the results for survey questions and includes a cross-analysis function for question pairs. In the comparison mode, users can select multiple occupation categories and compare them through radar charts (Figure 22).

Figure 22: Cross-occupation comparison using a radar chart

The example compares selected occupation categories (on top) across response options for a question on documenting practices.

The two interactive applications described in Sections 4.2.2 and 4.2.3 provide complementary perspectives for browsing and analysing the ECHOES consultation results: a profile-based perspective, mainly linked to digital practices, and an occupation-based perspective, linked to professional roles.

4.2.4 Translating profiles into personas

Building on this analytical foundation, the following step consisted of translating user profiles into personas, to provide a more accessible and human-centred interpretation of the findings. While clusters describe patterns in the data, personas bring these patterns to life by framing them in terms of concrete roles, motivations and challenges. The development of personas followed a synthesis process combining quantitative evidence and qualitative interpretation. Cluster characteristics, cross-tabulations and recurring patterns were complemented by insights from open-ended responses and by iterative discussions with project partners. This allowed the identification of a set of representative figures embodying typical ways of engaging with cultural heritage data and digital infrastructures.

Figure 23: List of personas

In brackets the cluster profile they have been derived from.

Each persona reflects a coherent combination of professional context, goals, frustrations and expectations, and is designed to make explicit how different types of users may interact with the future Cultural Heritage Cloud. Particular attention was paid to ensuring consistency across personas, while also capturing the diversity of roles, levels of digital maturity and attitudes towards data.

The personas developed within the project include, among others: research-oriented data producers, technical developers, cultural communicators, institutional data stewards, independent professionals, domain specialists, low-digital practitioners, governance-oriented actors, interoperability experts and academic professionals.

Personas are conceived not as fixed representations, but as a dynamic tool supporting multiple stages of the project. They facilitate communication across work packages, support co-design workshops and validation activities, and help identify both shared and profile-specific needs. In particular, they provide a practical framework for discussing user requirements, testing assumptions, and identifying potential gaps in the current analysis.

The full set of personas is presented in the tables below, where each persona is presented through a structured sheet including role and context, goals, frustrations and needs in relation to the Cultural Heritage Cloud.

Persona: Research Data Scientist

Name	Dr. Anna Olsen
Role & context	Researcher producing and analysing digital datasets in academic and research projects
Profile	Researcher / data producer – University or research institute
Goals	Produce reproducible research; publish datasets; analyse data
Frustrations	Metadata effort; fragmented repositories; unclear licensing
Needs	FAIR workflows; metadata tools; trusted repositories; licensing guidance

Persona: Digital Tool Builder

Name	Marco Rossi
Role & context	Develops tools, platforms and APIs for cultural heritage
Profile	Developer / data engineer – SME, RI, innovation unit
Goals	Build interoperable tools; connect systems; reuse solutions
Frustrations	Translating user needs; poor data quality; lack of standards
Needs	APIs; reusable datasets; documentation; testing environments

Persona: Storyteller for Heritage

Name	Sofia Dimitriou
Role & context	Uses heritage data for communication, education and engagement
Profile	Mediator / educator – Museum, NGO, media
Goals	Engage audiences; create content; expand reach
Frustrations	Lack of reusable data; unclear licensing; poor usability
Needs	User-friendly tools; curated data; storytelling tools

Persona: Collections Steward

Name	Claire Hewitt
Role & context	Manages collections, documentation and long-term preservation
Profile	Curator / archivist – GLAM
Goals	Ensure access; maintain quality; support policies
Frustrations	Legacy systems; workload; legal complexity
Needs	Preservation tools; vocabularies; governance support

Persona: Independent Heritage Consultant

Name	Luis Fernández
Role & context	Freelance heritage professional
Profile	Consultant – freelance / SME
Goals	Deliver services; remain competitive; reuse data
Frustrations	Limited infrastructure; lack of support; training cost
Needs	Affordable tools; storage; training

Persona: Domain / Subject Specialist

Name	Dr. Elena Novak
Role & context	Applies domain expertise in heritage research and practice
Profile	Specialist – heritage institution
Goals	Maintain standards; produce quality data; link fieldwork and digital
Frustrations	Lack of context; poor discoverability; generic tools
Needs	Domain-aware tools; filtering; provenance

Persona: Low-Digital Practitioner

Name	Maria Bianchi
Role & context	Works with minimal digital tools
Profile	Heritage professional – small institution
Goals	Perform tasks simply; minimal digitisation
Frustrations	Lack of skills; limited support
Needs	Simple tools; training; assistance

Persona: FAIR Data Champion

Name	Alex Turner
Role & context	Promotes FAIR and governance frameworks
Profile	Data steward – university / RI
Goals	Promote openness; improve governance; implement FAIR
Frustrations	Resistance; inconsistent standards; legal issues
Needs	Licensing frameworks; repositories; FAIR tools

Persona: Interoperability Engineer

Name	Thomas Becker
Role & context	Works on semantic modelling and integration
Profile	Semantic engineer – RI
Goals	Achieve interoperability; enable linked data
Frustrations	Metadata inconsistency; lack of standards
Needs	Mapping tools; ontologies; validation pipelines

Persona: Heritage Scholar

Name	Dr. James Whitaker
Role & context	Academic combining research, teaching and engagement
Profile	Researcher / lecturer – university
Goals	Conduct research; teach; integrate outputs
Frustrations	Fragmented data; poor integration
Needs	Data access; tools; training materials

Persona: Early Career Explorer

Name	Luca Marinelli
Role & context	Early-stage professional developing skills
Profile	Student / junior researcher
Goals	Build skills; grow network
Frustrations	Lack of mentorship; unclear entry points
Needs	Training; onboarding; mentoring

4.3 Mapping of communities

The consultation activities, and particularly the survey, have provided a comprehensive overview of the heritage landscape, as described in the previous sections. This body of information supported the development of an integrated Atlas representing both the heritage practice-driven ecosystem and the users' needs within the digital environment.

The Atlas of communities is conceived as a complex, multilayered diagram composed of four interconnected layers, each illustrating different dimensions of the heritage ecosystem and the digital environment of the Cloud. To better capture the diversity and complexity of the Cultural Heritage Cloud communities, the Atlas was designed as a modular representation in which each layer can also be extracted and analysed independently.

The circular structure of the diagram reflects the integrated and interdependent nature of its elements, actors, practices, and governance levels. The first three layers are heritage-related and represent the professional and institutional dimensions of the heritage ecosystem. While the participation of volunteers and civil society is acknowledged across these dimensions, their role is understood as integrated within, and often guided by, the professional heritage context (e.g. Blue Shield).

Although this was not applied as a strict rule, a coherent approach guided both the design and the positioning of elements within each layer. Elements were arranged according to their interdependencies, their functions, and their proximity to heritage assets, both tangible and intangible, moving progressively from the core towards the outer sections of the diagram.

The outer layer highlights other sectors and fields of practice that either play a key supporting role for the heritage sector or may represent future contributors to, and users of, the Cloud. This layer also reflects more commercially oriented and service-led dimensions which, although not necessarily direct users of the Cloud, may nevertheless benefit from its broader uptake and expansion.

An additional structural component was introduced to support the organisation and clustering of elements: three axes inspired by the ECHOES pillars, representing the Cloud's broader mandate towards heritage and society. These axes – Knowledge, Innovation, and Culture – act as conceptual poles that help organise and cluster the different elements across the diagram.

- Knowledge represents the production and exchange of knowledge about and around heritage;
- Innovation represents technological and digital development;
- Culture represents the cultural dimension, heritage-led activities, and societal engagement.

Heritage assets themselves act as the implicit core anchor of the diagram, while the three axes provide a degree of vertical alignment across the first three layers.

The connecting lines should be understood as visual guides rather than rigid boundaries or hierarchical structures. Likewise, none of the layers should be interpreted as exhaustive or absolute representations of their respective dimensions.

The first three layers describe the heritage sector and its professional practices. Their elements derive mainly from the WP4 survey and other consultation activities and aim to represent the potential user communities of the Cloud in their many different forms. The fourth layer results from the broader ECHOES efforts, as well as contributions from other work packages, to better understand the digital transformation of the sector. Its purpose is to incorporate the technical dimension of the Cloud and illustrate its capacity to respond to the needs and expectations of the various communities.

Figure 24: Layer 1 - Individuals

The first layer focuses on individuals. It aims to capture the professional roles and practitioners active within the heritage sector, identifying the occupations and profiles that constitute the future users of the Cloud.

Figure 25: Layer 2 - Institutions

The second layer maps institutions with responsibilities and mandates related to heritage, encompassing different levels of governance and including organised civil society organisations. It represents the collective and organisational context within which heritage professionals and researchers operate.

Figure 26: Layer 3 - Functions and objectives

The third layer maps the functions and objectives of professional and research actors within the cultural heritage sector, reflecting their principal activities and responsibilities. For clarity, the detailed clustering of activities associated with these objectives and functions has been removed from the visual representation and is presented separately below.

The red titles (functions and objectives) are presented below and include – but are not limited to – the following activities:

Law enforcement:

- Legal protection
- Protection against illicit trafficking
- Risk assessment

Heritage research and studies:

- Attribution
- Dating
- Context studies
- Provenance research
- Heritage studies
- Visualisation
- Characterisation
- Deterioration analysis
- Conservation treatments

CH conservation and preservation:

- Preventive conservation
- Visualisation
- Characterisation
- Deterioration analysis
- Conservation treatments

Urban and spatial planning:

- Preventive conservation
- Site management and maintenance

Museology and heritage management:

- Inventory, cataloguing
- Storage
- Exhibition planning
- Heritage studies
- Museography

Digital support and service provision:

- Digital infrastructures and database management and maintenance
- Computer sciences and developing

Documentation, archiving and information management:

- Inventory, cataloguing
- Attribution
- Dating
- Context studies
- Provenance research
- Long-term preservation of information (data and analogue)

Mediation and audience engagement:

- Publication
- Heritage interpretation and mediation
- Community-building

Art trading:

- Sale of cultural goods

Artistic creation:

- Artistic creation (contemporary art)
- Design
- Crafts
- Festivals
- Traditional performances
- Music
- Video gaming

Figure 27: Layer 4 - Digital needs, tools and norms

The fourth layer presents the main digital needs, tools, and norms identified so far through ECHOES activities, particularly the WP4 work investigating the various communities. The transversal needs shared across disciplines, fields, and professions are represented in the blue circle and derive directly from the ECHOES consultation results. The left side of the orange outer circle includes the Cloud tools currently being developed by the sister project. The right side presents the components and services that will be incorporated into the Cloud to address the digital needs identified through the consultation process. This fourth layer showcases the potential of the full Cultural Heritage Cloud to address users' needs.

The Atlas of the communities is therefore understood as the combination of all these dimensions converging to the Cloud infrastructure, overcoming the diversity and complexity of heritage practice and research, reframing it through a collaborative digital environment accessible to all.

4.4 Representativeness analysis

The survey allowed a sound snapshot of the different types of professionals that represent the potential Cloud federated communities, but it is also acknowledged the need for further targeted reach-out actions to achieve the widest engagement possible. The representativeness of the survey respondents, or the lack of it, shows some bias of the results and, consequently, in the analysis undertaken. In general terms, diversity and representation gaps in the respondents' sample can be inferred by analysing, in particular, questions from A, B, and some from the C sections.

A case in point, already mentioned in the analysis of C2, is that the survey was circulated in English. This might have prevented those who don't master English sufficiently well to fully understand the survey topics and concepts from engaging with the survey.

This is reflected in the responses to C2, where accessibility support for non-English speakers had the lowest score among the identified challenges and impediments. Conversely, when asked in C3 what can be improved, the need to support multiple European languages and scripts, accessibility features, and interfaces adapted to diverse user groups ranked among the top ten requests from respondents, indicating awareness of this issue.

Another key point to consider in the analysis of survey representativeness is that respondents were often allowed multiple answers. Therefore, the relative weight of each possible answer within a question must be taken into account when interpreting trends. Nevertheless, these survey shortcomings can be mitigated by identifying the potential bias and taking action to address the unbalanced coverage of respondents. This can be achieved through the complementary consultation activities of WP4 to deepen and better understand the diversity of communities of the Cloud.

Digital familiarity

A key takeaway here is the dropout point of the survey, which occurs when respondents enter Section C – Digital tools and resources: current needs and practices – where more than 30% of respondents left the survey. This section is the first to explore the use of specific digital tools in professional practice. It uses technical terms and concepts that imply some familiarity with digital tools.

This suggests that the dropout pattern may be linked to low familiarity with digital practices or difficulties in fully understanding the concepts used and indicates that part of the sample may include professionals with limited digital engagement. This is a key target for ECHOES, as it aims to promote digital practices, particularly among those currently less engaged in digital environments.

Another positive insight lies in question C1 (sub-questions a, b, c), where respondents could answer “yes”, “would like to” or “no”. In all sub-questions, the responses “yes” and “would like to” consistently outnumber negative answers. This highlights a predisposition and willingness to adopt digital practices among these respondents.

Further into the survey, respondents were also asked about the main difficulties preventing them from further engaging with digital practices. This is where ECHOES can provide solutions and possible ways forward.

ECHOES must therefore devise ways to further reach current non-digital or low-digital professionals among the wider community of heritage practitioners. It must also thoroughly analyse the major challenges and expectations of these professionals to promote their uptake of the Cloud infrastructure.

Territorial representation

As mentioned earlier, the survey shows uneven territorial coverage across the EU. Approximately 25% of respondents are based in France, Portugal and Italy, while another 25% are distributed across Spain, Bulgaria, Greece, Germany, Finland, the United Kingdom, Slovenia, Austria and Belgium. Other EU countries have even lower representation, highlighting particularly limited participation from Eastern, Baltic and Northern countries. This territorial coverage was not broad enough for a meaningful cross-country analysis, as this would bear a natural bias, delivering a narrow reality across Europe.

Nevertheless, ECHOES’ complementary consultation activities aim to strengthen engagement with professionals across many of the EU countries and regions with particular focus on those less captured by the survey.

Professional sample

Universities and research institutions are the most represented workplace type (40%), followed at some distance by libraries, archives and museums (23%) and historical monuments, buildings and sites (8.6%). Together, these account for more than all other types of workplaces combined, such as companies, trade associations, non-profit organisations or galleries (question A5).

When these findings are considered alongside the reported fields of activity (question A6), where the three most frequently reported activities — conservation and preservation, research in the social sciences and humanities, and education, mediation and audience engagement — account for 50% of all responses, they indicate that the majority of respondents are mainly institutionally based, with a strong focus on research, heritage studies and academic education.

This institutional representativeness is confirmed by responses on the types of organisation respondents work for (A4), where around 67% reported working for public non-profit organisations, and by employment status (A2), where 71% reported being employed.

Another possible insight concerns the particular focus on heritage conservation and preservation, which is only one of the core heritage professional activities but accounts for 23% of reported activities. This may be interpreted as extending beyond practical heritage preservation and conservation to include studies and research around and about the topic.

Universities and research infrastructures represent 40% of the institutions where respondents work, whereas core heritage institutions combined represent 32% (including libraries, archives, museums, historical monuments, listed buildings and sites). This can be linked to another key aspect: the low representation of museology and collection management (8.6%) in relation to the high score of the LAM group (23%), possibly indicating lower engagement from respondents working in more heritage-led practice.

Other low representations relevant to the heritage ecosystem can be perceived by combining answers from A5 and A6. The built environment is not strongly represented: it is the least represented core heritage institution type in the responses, and urban planning appears very low among professional activities. Using the same combination of questions, the survey also shows limited engagement from the CCIs, with the lowest responses coming from “Galleries and exhibition places” and “Artistic creation and art market”.

Finally, another key aspect worth taking into consideration is the low engagement of professionals operating in the private sector. Those working in private for-profit organisations (A4) represent 12% of responses, which is aligned with responses related to working conditions (A2), where the combined answers “self-employed/freelancer” and “business owner/entrepreneur” add up to 19% of responses.

This part of the labour market representation should be further explored, as those operating in the private sector often deliver services to public institutions, work in public-private partnerships, and represent a significant portion of the heritage labour force.

The demographic group of respondents

This analysis must take into account that respondents could answer either as representatives of an institution or in their own individual capacity. In this context, and as mentioned above, respondents predominantly have an academic degree, with 50% already holding a PhD, and 65% are women. The most represented age group is 46–55 (32%), followed by 36–45 (27%), 26–35 (18%) and 56–65 (16%).

None of these features is surprising, as the heritage sector, like the cultural and creative sectors more broadly, has a strong female presence across the majority of occupations. In light of the professional and institutional characteristics described above, the predominance of doctorates is also understandable.

Further engagement will be devised to reach younger generations and early-career professionals, to assess their needs and predisposition to interact with the Cloud. They represent the next generation of professionals and researchers.

5. Communities' needs and expectations

In conducting a thorough analysis of the survey results to map the needs and expectations of the federated heritage community regarding the Cultural Heritage Cloud, we should first consider the 'human' factor: the professional DNA of the cultural heritage sector. At a higher, cross-sectional level, this forms certain aspects of the professional mindset and behaviour, which are common to the different sub-communities of professionals.

Professionals in the CH sector operate with a "stewardship first" mentality. Their primary drive is the long-term preservation and ethical protection of heritage, which often makes them cautious about digital transition. They have a value-led approach, they prioritise cultural values, society, historical accuracy and authenticity over pure technological speed. Digital tools are viewed not as an end, but as a means to ease their work, democratise access to the heritage assets and to knowledge about them.

There is deep-rooted appreciation and respect for cultural assets, both tangible and intangible, while there remains a degree of wariness regarding "big tech" clouds, which raises/leads to concerns about data ownership, privacy, intellectual property, and long-term digital decay.

While the field thrives on interdisciplinary knowledge, where archaeology or art history meet physical and computer sciences, work is often carried out in isolated departments. Versus this fragmentation, there is an overall expectation for the Cultural Heritage Cloud to be a digital commons – a secure, non-commercial, and legally safe space that 'speaks their language' and not just a storage folder. The majority of professionals deal with physical objects and 'unstructured' real-world data. They expect the Cloud to provide a 'Digital Continuum', in which a 3D model – which serves as a digital twin of the physical object – is seamlessly linked to the object's physical history, maintenance and conservation reports, and legal status.

The analysis of the results is structured to bridge the gap between a universal infrastructure and specialised professional practice. A first higher-level analysis can identify the foundational floor, common requirements (open access, security, storage, and basic documentation) and behavioural patterns that apply to all users regardless of their specific role or profile. A second level of analysis identifies the expert ceiling, the specialised tools and workflows (like semantic modelling for managers or high-performance 3D processing and rendering for researchers) required by specific professional personas to fulfil their unique missions.

5.1 Transversal needs

The primary objective of the Cultural Heritage Cloud is to transcend the current landscape of digital fragmentation and the frequent sectoral siloed expertise. Historically, cultural heritage data has been sequestered within institutional repositories or lost in the ephemeral local storage of independent researchers and heritage practitioners. Such practice is also put in evidence in the ECHOES consultation (see question D9). The Cloud is designed to serve as a shared platform – a "Digital Commons" – where heritage professionals and researchers access data, scientific resources, and high-level tools tailored to the unique ethical and technical demands of the sector.

To unify this federated community, the consultation reveals several foundational needs that cut across every profile. These are the non-negotiables for Cloud adoption:

Need 1: Accessibility of tools and services

The provision of high-level digital resources, tools and services that are financially and technically reachable for all actors, regardless of their institutional affiliation or budget size.

Barriers & Limitations: A clear barrier to accessibility of digital services and resources is costs and licensing: Software, hardware, subscriptions, and storage infrastructure can be expensive and difficult to sustain under limited institutional budgets or even more for independent researchers, or freelance professionals. Prohibitive costs of proprietary software and high-end hardware are the primary obstacles, especially for Freelancers (41.5%) and Cultural Communicators (26.9%).

The Challenge: The Cloud must provide free or low-cost open-source alternatives that do not require expensive local computing power to run.

Need 2: Seamless interoperability and user-centred design

Regardless of professional status, there is a high demand for systems that 'talk' to one another (see answers to C2.1 and C3.1). Interoperability and Integration difficulties come first when using digital tools and resources, while low complexity and user friendliness of the UIs are equally important to users. Multilingual accessibility and inclusive design are also important. The creation of an ecosystem where disparate systems can exchange data without loss, managed through intuitive, multilingual interfaces is commonly expected.

Barriers & Limitations: Persistent difficulties in connecting tools, infrastructures and data environments are a major concern, cited by 40% of Technical Developers and 33.3% of Academia.

The Challenge: UX and UI are often secondary to functionality in CH tools. The Cloud must harmonise complex backend integration with a front-end that requires a shallow

learning curve and offers tools presenting improved usability through co-creative approaches in their design and development through feedback from user-cases and real-life scenarios.

Need 3: Data findability and FAIR availability

Ensuring that cultural heritage assets – both digital and undigitised – are discoverable through standardized, high-quality metadata and non-restrictive access policies. Many archives remain undigitised, or unfindable, due to the lack of public metadata while paywalls, restricted access policies, or reluctance to share data may limit research opportunities.

Barriers & Limitations: Many resources remain undigitised (52.7% for Practitioners) or lack public metadata. The limited adoption of metadata standards and ontologies, incomplete metadata, and weak alignment with FAIR principles or semantic models hinder interoperability and reuse.

The Challenge: Overcoming the hesitancy to share caused by Legal/IPR constraints (cited by >50% across profiles) and the low adoption of shared semantic models like ontologies (only 16.9% for Anchors).

Need 4: Automated tools for data quality and preparation

The implementation of (AI-driven? or simple to use) tools to assist in the cleaning, documentation, and "sharing-readiness" of datasets to reduce the manual burden on professionals. To foster a culture of openness, the Cloud must offer automated documentation and metadata extraction tools.

Barriers & Limitations: A major behavioural barrier identified is the high level of effort required to prepare data for sharing. Across all profiles, "Situational Sharing" (Yes, sometimes) is the dominant behaviour. 57.4% of Researchers and 50% of Practitioners cite the "extra effort" of preparation as the reason they only share "sometimes." Data quality & validation (inconsistent, erroneous, or heterogeneous data requires harmonization and cleaning) data quality dependent on complex systems of data validation.

The Challenge: Moving from "Situational Sharing" to "Systemic Sharing" requires the Cloud to offer automated metadata extraction as well as HTR and OCR tools to digitise the non-digitised materials (26.9-52.7%) currently acting as a bottleneck.

Need 5: Hybrid data management and storage

A reliable storage infrastructure that respects the "hybrid" nature of CH work, allowing for seamless transition between local, institutional, and cloud environments.

Barriers & Limitations: Fragmentation of storage – 75.9% of Researchers and 74% of Freelance professionals store the majority of their data locally, which creates a high risk of data loss.

Institutional servers are also prominent, with 56% of Scientific data producers using them, indicating a significant reliance on organisation-managed infrastructures.

Cloud-based commercial platforms are used by 38% of scientific data producers, while self-hosted environments account for around 30%. Among Freelance professionals, commercial cloud platforms are used more frequently, with 50.9% indicating that more than half of their data (>50%) are stored on services such as Google Drive or Dropbox.

The Challenge: Only 31% of Scientific data producers follow a formal Data Management Plan (DMP). The Cloud must integrate "DMP-by-design," making professional data management an automated part of the workflow rather than an administrative chore.

Need 6: Nuanced access governance and trust-based sharing

The transition from binary "Open/Closed" access to nuanced, granular access governance ranging from 'open' to 'upon request' or for 'specific purposes' protects Intellectual Property and prevents data misuse.

Barriers & Limitations: Sharing is mediated by legal and IPR concerns (over 50% across all profiles) as well as concerns about misuse, particularly for Institutional Anchors (49.3%).

The Challenge: Creating a 'Safe Commons', an environment that addresses Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) and privacy concerns, where professionals feel secure sharing sensitive data or archival material. The governance model must support "upon request" or "purpose-specific" access to satisfy the 57.4% of Practitioners concerned about confidentiality.

Need 7: Secure collaborative environments for research

Virtual workspaces that allow cross-profile teams (e.g., a Curator, a Conservator-Restorer, a Heritage Scientist and a Developer) to collaborate on sensitive data while ensuring privacy, GDPR and IPR compliance.

Barriers & Limitations: Inconsistent authentication practices – Freelancers use Google (69%) while Anchors use Institutional logins (95%). Concerns repeatedly mentioned by all profiles are confidentiality and privacy, legal or contractual restrictions, concerns about misuse, and technical barriers.

The Challenge: The Cloud must ensure Identity & access management, privacy, trust, and integrity to provide environments where collaborative research can happen without the data ever being "at risk" or improperly circulated.

Need 8: Integrated workflows across the data lifecycle

The need for integrated environments that support the full lifecycle of cultural heritage data, from the management of primary data - collected, digitised, or analytically acquired on tangible or intangible heritage assets- to the processing, analysis, interpretation, semantic representation, sharing, and long-term preservation of data and related knowledge.

Barriers & Limitations: Current workflows are significantly fractured along institutional, professional, and technical boundaries and often fragmented across multiple tools and environments, requiring manual transitions between systems. This fragmentation manifests across different user profiles, leading to inefficiencies, duplication of effort and increased risk of data loss or inconsistency. For example, while 85 % of Researchers and 80 % of Scientific Data Producers create data to address complex research questions, their practices are siloed: 76 % of Researchers store their primary datasets locally, and only 31% follow a formal Data Management Plan (DMP). This structural isolation makes transitioning data from fieldwork or computational modelling (41%) into long-term repositories highly insecure.

The Challenge: The Cloud must enable seamless transitions between different stages of work, reducing fragmentation and supporting continuous, end-to-end processes across heterogeneous tools and infrastructures.

Need 9: Sustainable and reliable digital infrastructures

The need for long-term stability and sustainability of digital tools, systems and infrastructures, minimising the impact of rapid technological obsolescence and reducing the burden of constant updates and system changes.

Barriers & Limitations: The cultural heritage sector suffers from a fundamental misalignment between the long-term nature of heritage data preservation and the short, volatile lifecycles of modern digital technologies. Disrupted workflows and additional costs and maintenance burdens are created by short software life cycles, discontinued tools and frequent updates, particularly for institutions with limited resources and independent professionals. Anchors and Professional Heritage Practitioners operate in environments where financial and resource constraints are pervasive (36 % for Anchors). Coupled with limited staffing capacity (24 %) and significant skills gaps (33 %), these organisations simply lack the dedicated IT workforce to handle constant software updates or re-engineer pipelines when tools are suddenly discontinued. Freelancers, in particular, are highly sensitive to software instability, given that they rely heavily (82%) on free, open-access tools, due to financial constraints.

The Challenge: The Cloud must provide stable, well-maintained and interoperable solutions that ensure continuity over time, aligning technological evolution with the long-term nature of cultural heritage work.

Need 10: Continuous capacity building and user support

The need for ongoing training, guidance and support to enable users with different levels of digital maturity to adopt and use digital tools and services effectively.

Barriers & Limitations: The cultural heritage community is highly fragmented in terms of digital literacy and operational capacity. This creates a significant barrier to the uniform adoption of cloud technology. A lack of structured training opportunities, insufficient documentation and the complexity of tools create barriers to adoption, particularly for low-digital users and non-technical professionals. There is a clear asymmetry in digital maturity within the cultural heritage sector, ranging from highly technical semantic engineers who master advanced ontologies (46.4%) to non-technical actors who lack the necessary minimum training to deliver datasets ready for sharing. This divide further amplifies the system integration and data complexity issues (26.4%) reported by developers, while overburdened institutional anchors and heritage practitioners are hindered by significant skills gaps (33.3%), severe staffing shortages (23.8%) and a substantial physical backlog of non-digitised materials (52.7%). Freelancers are equally vulnerable: 30.2% cite significant learning barriers and skills gaps that prevent them from being active co-creators of the digital ecosystem.

The Challenge: The Cloud must provide accessible learning resources, clear documentation and user support mechanisms, fostering continuous capacity building across the community and ensuring inclusive participation in the digital ecosystem.

Significant differences in behavioural patterns emerge when comparing the 'Institutional Anchors' (who have a stable organisational context) with the 'Freelance & Self-Employed', who adopt a project-based approach. Although both groups share a high commitment to data sharing, their approaches to data flow - from the creation and documentation to long-term storage and reuse- as well as the barriers they face are entirely different.

Institutional Anchors (LAM institutions, universities, research centres, governmental agencies or public authorities, historical monuments, listed buildings, etc. (see the 'Institutional Anchors' profile, n=71)) operate within a structured, protected ecosystem. In terms of Infrastructure, they are the primary users of Institutional NAS/Servers (59.1%), and 38% are using data management and storage tools or services. For them, the Cloud is an extension of their office in the institutional setup. For authentication, their digital identity is institutional. With 95.8% using Institutional Logins, they expect the Cloud to recognise their university or museum credentials (SSO and EduGAIN) immediately. They look for system interoperability, scalability and long-term archiving (cited by 20% as a priority improvement).

On the opposite, Freelance and Self-Employed professionals (see the 'Freelance & Self-Employed' profile, n=104) operate in a heterogeneous, high-risk environment. Lacking institutional backing, 74% rely on local storage on personal devices and 50.9% on commercial clouds (Google, Dropbox). For authentication they are using commercial

identities (69.2% Google, 39.4 % Microsoft), but also institutional credentials (47.1%). Their primary barrier is cost (41.5%). They expect the Cloud to provide access to free or open-source versions of expensive tools (3D, GIS) that they currently pay for out-of-pocket.

This distinction would determine how the Cultural Heritage Cloud should handle authentication, storage and tool access for all. The Cloud must speak the language of IT Departments for the Anchors, while remaining as user-friendly and affordable as a consumer app for the Freelancers.

5.2 Community-specific needs

While transversal needs establish the foundation for Cloud adoption, a granular analysis of community or detailed breakdown per persona and cluster/profile-specific insights is vital to integrate the platform into professional workflows and deliver high-level, daily value (see Section 4.2 for a detailed description of the cluster profiles and personas).

The Research and Scientific Production profile

The Academia & Research and Scientific Data Producer profiles, which are partly overlapping, represent the users who are the most technically engaged and research-intensive.

This cluster represents the academic core of the consultation (108 respondents), and consists of highly qualified professionals, ranging from doctoral students to senior professors, who are embedded in universities, research institutes, and public infrastructures. While the Academia profile focuses on the broad generation of scholarly insights across disciplines, the Scientific Data Producer sub-group represents a more technically advanced layer. Together, they form a community of technical experts who manage the entire data lifecycle, from fieldwork, 3D and spatial documentation to complex computational analysis and long-term archiving.

Conceptualisation of the Cloud

For these users, the Cloud is envisioned as a unified, high-performance working environment. Rather than a separate, external platform, they expect it to function as a natural, integrated extension of their institutional workspace. They view the Cloud as a Digital Research Infrastructure that should seamlessly bridge the gap between their local data production and the collaborative European research ecosystem.

Workflow integration and objectives

The primary driver for this group is knowledge production; 85.2% of researchers and 80% of data producers create data specifically to address research questions. Their workflows are multidisciplinary, and involve:

- **Advanced documentation:** Heavy reliance on 3D scanning, modelling, and spatial /GIS technologies (79% among data producers).
- **Methodological diversity:** Archival research (72%), fieldwork (59%) and computational modelling (41%).
- **Multifaceted outputs:** In addition to scholarly papers, their workflow produces educational materials (52.8%), conservation plans (52%), and cataloguing metadata (59%), demonstrating that their scientific work serves broad applications and functions.

Major needs and expectations

To upgrade their work from "fragmented" to "federated," the Cloud must address deep-seated technical and organisational constraints:

- **Enhanced technical infrastructure:** To overcome current financial and resource constraints (35.6%), the Cloud must provide affordable access to high-end tools such as AI, machine learning, and 3D rendering, which are currently difficult to sustain on limited budgets.
- **Seamless system interoperability:** Addressing the 33.3% who report integration difficulties, the Cloud must implement shared community standards to allow data to flow between different analytical platforms without manual re-processing.
- **Advanced automation:** To reduce the significant effort currently required for data preparation, this group expects the Cloud to offer AI-based functionalities for automated documentation and metadata extraction.
- **Secure governance:** They seek to replace fragmented storage solutions with a secure, collaborative framework that offers stronger legal and security safeguards (20%), ensuring that their valuable research data is protected, sustainably managed, and reusable at scale.

The Institutional Anchors profile

The Institutional Anchors (71 respondents) are the professionals operating within Library, Archive, and Museum (LAM) environments, universities, and governmental agencies. This profile is characterised by high organisational responsibility: nearly 38% are directly involved in managing their institution's databases, servers, or repositories. They are the primary handlers of digital representations (66.2%) and physical collections, acting as the key connectors between material heritage and the digital infrastructure

that sustains it. They are particularly interested in digital tools supporting the annotation, analysis and management of cultural heritage data, as well as for automated approaches including handwriting or text recognition technologies such as HTR or OCR (19.7%) and automated analysis of textual or speech resources using natural language processing techniques (18.3%).

Conceptualisation of the Cloud

For institutional anchors, the cloud is envisaged as a secure, federated extension of the institutional repository. They do not see it as a replacement for their institutional systems, but rather as a trusted 'digital common' that provides the scalability and interoperability that their local infrastructures currently lack. Their perspective is heavily influenced by stewardship and continuity; they expect the cloud to provide a stable environment in which institutional identities and data security are strictly maintained.

Workflow integration & objectives

This cluster's workflows lie on the pathway from primary documentation to institutional management:

- **Production and digitisation:** 71.8% are engaged in digitisation, transcription, and 3D/spatial documentation, moving physical assets into the digital realm.
- **Knowledge and preservation:** Their primary objectives are answering research questions (78.9%) and archiving information (63.4%), closely followed by cataloguing and metadata creation (54.9%).
- **Authentication as a gateway:** Their workflow is strictly mediated by institutional security, with a 95.8% relying on institutional login systems (SSO and EduGAIN). Any Cloud integration must comply with the organisation's IT infrastructure to be adopted.

Major needs and expectations

To move institutional data into the shared Cloud space, it must address the following issues:

- **Solving interoperability issues:** This is a priority for this group (36.7%). They expect the Cloud to act as a "translator" between isolated institutional storage servers and the broader heritage ecosystem.
- **Resource and skills bridge:** They face significant financial and resource constraints (35.7%) and skills gaps (33.3%) are commonplace. They are looking to the cloud to provide user-friendly, automated tools that will reduce the technical burden on their limited staff.

- **Trust through granular governance:** Data sharing is currently "situational" rather than systematic due to concerns about data misuse (49.3%) and the quality of metadata (60.6%). They expect the Cloud to offer conditional access, enabling them to maintain control over who has access to what and for what purpose.
- **Collaborative scalability:** They expect the Cloud to facilitate stronger collaboration frameworks (23.3%) and provide storage scalability (20%) that individual institutions often struggle to fund independently.

Professional Heritage Practitioners profile

Professional Heritage Practitioners (n=188), unlike the Academia and Research cluster, which may prioritise experimental or computational innovation, this group is anchored in the operational realities of preservation, regulatory compliance, and the day-to-day management of physical and archival assets.

Conceptualisation of the Cloud

For this profile, as for the Institutional anchors, the Cloud is perceived as a functional extension of the institutional repository. Their conceptualisation is defined by security, compliance, and continuity.

- **Institutional server vs. Commercial cloud:** 59.1% rely on institutional servers, considering them to be the gold standard for data security. Although 28.7% of respondents use commercial clouds, these are often considered secondary storage solutions rather than permanent repositories for heritage assets. Practitioners view the cloud as a tool that can bridge the technological delay between large national institutions and smaller local sites, aiming for a unified "digital continuum" rather than fragmented institutional repositories.
- **Trust and risk:** Their view is heavily filtered through a lens of legal and privacy concerns (57.4%). The cloud is "safe" only if it guarantees that confidentiality and contractual restrictions are upheld.

Workflow integration and objectives

Unlike researchers who produce data to test hypotheses and address research questions, professional practitioners produce data to support preservation. Their workflow is conservation-oriented.

- **Integration level:** Technological adoption is selective and pragmatic. High-end tools (3D scanning, LiDAR) are integrated into specific workflows like restoration planning (56.9%) rather than being used for general exploration and research.
- **Documentation as workflow:** Documentation is not an optional step but the foundation of the work. Simple notes and manual annotation files (41.5%) often

start the process. Metadata filling (29.8%) and documentation systems (22.9%) are essential for long-term institutional archiving.

- **Primary objectives:** Archiving/Preserving: 88.3%, Cataloguing: 61.7%, Conservation-Restoration Planning: 56.9%

Major needs and expectations

The needs of this group are infrastructure-first rather than innovation-first. They seek stability and lower barriers to entry for existing technologies.

Key Barriers

- **Resource scarcity:** Financial constraints and budget limitations are the dominant inhibitors of digital maturity.
- **The preparation gap:** 52.7% struggle with non-digitised materials. The sheer volume of physical heritage that remains "offline" creates a bottleneck for any advanced digital strategy.
- **Interoperability issues:** A high need for systems that "talk to each other." Practitioners are frustrated by fragmented databases that require manual re-entry of data.

Expectations for improvement

- **Standardisation:** Stronger alignment with shared international standards to reduce the labour of data cleaning.
- **Capacity building:** There is a high demand for skill development to bridge the gap between traditional conservation and digital documentation.
- **Sustainable open source:** Expectations for affordable, open-source, or institutionally-backed solutions that won't disappear if a commercial vendor changes its pricing or goes out of business.

Freelance and self-employed Professionals

Freelance and self-employed Professionals (n=104) are characterised by high technical agility but limited institutional support. Unlike the Heritage Practitioners, who are anchored in stable institutional environments, freelancers' digital practices are shaped by cost-efficiency and client requirements.

Freelance professionals are independent experts (business owners, consultants, conservator-restorers) whose work is project-based and infrastructure-independent.

Conceptualisation of the Cloud

For freelancers, the "Cloud" is not a repository for long-term preservation; it is a collaborative workspace and a necessity for mobility

They store the majority of their data on commercial clouds (Google Drive, Dropbox) (50.9%). This is a clear contrast to the institutional servers favoured by practitioners. For the freelancer, the cloud would be the infrastructure.

Authentication as Access: Their digital identity is tied to commercial ecosystems – 69.2% use Google accounts for professional login. This reflects a need for seamless, low-friction access across different client platforms. They view the cloud as a place to hand over deliverables to clients rather than a space for permanent archival.

Workflow integration and objectives

Freelancer workflows are output-driven. Data production is a means to fulfil a contract, leading to a high reliance on "reusing" their own past knowledge bases (98.1% reuse their own data).

- **Integration Level:** They show higher adoption of specialised production technological solutions compared to practitioners. 61.5% engage with 3D scanning and 40.4% with GIS. Because they often sell specialised services (e.g., a 3D survey), these tools are central to their business model.
- **Documentation as a bottleneck:** Documentation is largely informal (54.8% simple notes). In a freelance model, structured metadata (22.1%) is often skipped unless explicitly required by a client.
- Their primary objectives are Reporting, fulfilling contractual obligations; Conservation-restoration planning: Applied technical intervention; Decision Support: providing expert evidence for stakeholders.

Major needs and expectations

Freelancers face the same technical challenges as institutions but without the safety net of a dedicated IT or legal department.

Key Barriers

- **Financial friction:** 41.5% cite cost as a major barrier. They are highly sensitive to "subscription fatigue" and rely heavily on free/open-access tools (81.7%).
- **Legal insecurity:** 50% are hampered by contractual or legal restrictions. Without institutional legal teams, they are often uncertain about their rights to the data they produce for clients.

- **Isolation from development:** Collaboration with technical teams is low. They are often "users" of finished products rather than "co-creators" of the tools they use.

Expectations for Improvement

- **Affordability:** A strong demand for tools that are accessible on a project-by-project basis or are open-source.
- **Interoperability:** They need to move data between different client systems without losing information.
- **Standardised guidelines:** Clearer rules for data sharing that protect their intellectual property while satisfying client needs.

The Freelancer is more technologically exploratory and mobile but operates relying on personal devices and commercial clouds with little formal data governance (only 4.8% have a DMP). The Practitioner has more stability and structure but may move more slowly in adopting new visualization and analysis technologies.

Data Documenters / Managers profile

These respondents (n=56) represent specialists dedicated to the systematic description, organisation, and long-term viability of heritage records – Metadata specialists, curators, digital archivists.

Conceptualisation of the Cloud

For Data Documenters, the Cloud is a governed archive. It is the transition point from "working data" to "permanent record."

Institutional security: 69.6% prioritise institutional servers. They view the Cloud through the lens of stewardship, expecting it to provide long-term preservation solutions (73.2%) rather than just temporary storage. Their conceptualization is defined by security tiers. They manage environments where access is strictly regulated (75% internal only), ensuring that data integrity is maintained according to institutional protocols.

Workflow integration and objectives

The workflow of a Documenter is standard-driven. They act as the quality control layer of the heritage lifecycle.

- **Integration level:** High involvement in tool design (66.1% as concept designers). They don't just use tools; they define the workflows that ensure data is "clean" and searchable.

- **Documentation as the output:** 85.7% focus on metadata filling and 71.4% on established protocols. For this profile, the documentation is a primary output.

Prioritised objectives

- **Improving dataset completeness:** 73.2% (The "Best Practice" drivers).
- **Supporting management and protection:** 66.1% (Informing conservation).
- **Public engagement:** 67.9% (Turning records into education).

Semantic Engineers & Data Architects profile

These respondents (n=56) represent engineers focused on connectivity, interoperability, and the machine-actionable nature of heritage data.

Conceptualisation of the Cloud

For the Semantic engineer, the Cloud is like a knowledge graph. It is not a place to store data, but a space to link it.

- **Linked Open Data (LOD):** They view the Cloud as a medium for Semantic alignment. They are the primary proponents of fully open access models (60.7%) because their work relies on data being discoverable by machines globally.
- They see the Cloud as a compute environment for running scripts, APIs, and automated data processing rather than a static information repository.

Workflow Integration and objectives

The workflow of a data architect is relationship-driven. They focus on how Data A relates to Data B across different institutional repositories.

- **Integration Level:** They operate at the backend. 50% manage object-oriented databases and 46.4% utilize advanced ontologies (CIDOC CRM, SKOS). They bridge the gap between "human-readable" notes and "machine-readable" code.
- **Automated documentation:** While they value metadata, they foster Automation and scripting (23.2% – the highest across profiles) to handle large-scale data ingestion.

Primary objectives

- **System interoperability:** Building the "pipes" between institutions.
- **Refining algorithms/models:** 42.9% (Creating the tools for visualisation).
- **Knowledge discovery:** Validating hypotheses through pattern recognition (51.8%).

Table 3: Comparison of major needs and expectations between data documenters and semantic engineers

	Data Documenters	Semantic Engineers
Major barrier	Resource: Lack of time to manually fill metadata (41.5%).	Complexity: Interoperability and system integration issues (26.4%)
Needs	User-friendly interfaces for manual entry (23.8%).	API integration and support for Graph/NoSQL databases.
Expectations	More training and shared standards (19.0%).	Stronger legal/governance frameworks for open data sharing.

Overall, the needs identified across the different user profiles show a high degree of convergence, with most community-specific barriers and expectations reflecting, or aligning with, the transversal needs outlined above. Rather than representing fundamentally different requirements, these variations highlight differences in priorities, capacities and operational contexts across user groups.

In this sense, the main distinction lies not in what is needed, but in how critical certain features are for different communities, and in their varying ability to adopt and benefit from them. Some users prioritise accessibility and ease of use, while others emphasise advanced functionalities, scalability or integration capabilities.

This reinforces the importance of designing the Cloud as a flexible and inclusive ecosystem, capable of addressing shared needs while accommodating different levels of digital maturity, resources and expertise, and supporting users through appropriate services, guidance and capacity building mechanisms.

5.3 Gap analysis as a result of matching between inventory and needs

Previous sections – covering both transversal and community-specific needs – have provided a foundational vision of the Cultural Heritage Cloud as a collaborative, interoperable, and user-centred digital infrastructure. These needs include demands for improved tools interoperability, reduced costs, better training, stronger data governance, and enhanced usability. A recurring theme is the reliance on existing tools and resources¹¹, with many communities already using specific software in their

¹¹ Here, we should highlight that in comparison to the mapping of interest analysis described in section 2.1, we rely on a slightly different definition of tools, reusing the one provided by the ECHOES Glossary. Digital tool is understood as “a software application, system, or device that uses digital technology to perform a specific task or set of tasks for a specific purpose” (definition currently available at: https://vocabs.ilc4clarin.ilc.cnr.it/vocabularies/echoes/digital_tool).

workflows. This raises a critical question: which tools are already available and could be reused or integrated into the Cloud? This question has been tackled by a collaboration between WPs 3 and 4 that worked towards a gap analysis to systematically identify:

- Existing tools that can be leveraged
- Where current solutions fall short (i.e. persistent gaps),
- And where the Cloud must focus to deliver added value beyond what is already available.

Following up on the methodology set up for the **ECHOES inventory** in MS8 (submitted in May 2025), the analysis carried out builds on the answers to five open-ended questions from the questionnaire¹² as they were identified as relevant sources from where to extract names of software, tools and databases, as well as semantic artefacts, such as controlled vocabularies and ontological models used by the respondents in their workflows. 447 resources were extracted from the answers to these questions, and were normalised and further enriched, by adding wherever possible a description, a URL, a resource type, an activity (or function of a resource), a license and providers' name.

To enable more meaningful comparison, the resources identified in the inventory were then clustered using a multi-layered and hybrid approach combining type, function, domain, and context to create 12 high-level categories:

1. **Digital heritage & cultural data management platforms:**

These platforms are the backbone of digital cultural heritage, enabling institutions to publish, preserve, and share collections at scale. Open-source platforms (Omeka, DSpace, Europeana) dominate, reflecting a strong commitment to open access.

2. **Specialised cultural heritage software & tools:**

This cluster represents the "hands-on" tools of cultural heritage work. The dominance of commercial software (Adobe, Autodesk) alongside powerful open-source alternatives (Blender, QGIS) shows a hybrid ecosystem where both accessibility and professional-grade capabilities coexist.

3. **Metadata, cataloguing & knowledge organisation systems:**

This cluster is the *lingua franca* of digital heritage. The widespread use of standards like CIDOC CRM, Dublin Core, and SKOS demonstrates a deep commitment to interoperability. Many are maintained by national institutions or international consortia.

¹² Answers to the following questions have been processed: D7.1, D8.1.1, E5, F2.1, F2.3.1.

4. Data analysis, visualisation & machine learning platforms:

This cluster is the analytical engine of research. The dominance of open-source tools (Python, R, KNIME, OpenRefine) and cloud-based platforms (Google Colab, Power BI) reflects a shift toward accessible, scalable, and collaborative data science. AI tools are rapidly becoming essential.

5. Geographic Information Systems (GIS) & spatial analysis tools:

GIS is fundamental for cultural heritage research involving sites, landscapes, and historical geography. The strong presence of both commercial (Esri) and open-source (QGIS, PostGIS) tools enables broad access. Web-based mapping (Leaflet, Google MyMaps) is key for public engagement.

6. Database & data storage systems:

This cluster provides the foundational infrastructure. The coexistence of traditional relational databases (PostgreSQL, MySQL) with modern NoSQL and semantic databases (MongoDB, GraphDB, Virtuoso) reflects the diversity of data types and use cases in digital humanities and cultural heritage.

7. Research & academic productivity suites:

These are the essential "office" tools for researchers. The dominance of Microsoft and Google reflects their ubiquity, while open-source alternatives (VS Code, LibreOffice) are critical for cost-effective and customizable workflows.

8. Scientific & engineering simulation & analysis software:

This cluster serves the intersection of cultural heritage with scientific analysis (e.g., material degradation, structural integrity). It highlights the interdisciplinary nature of modern heritage research, which requires specialised tools from engineering and physics.

9. Web development & content Management Systems (CMS):

These tools are the primary means of publishing research findings and managing digital collections online. WordPress and MediaWiki are the most common, enabling both simple websites and complex collaborative knowledge bases.

10. Digital preservation & file management tools:

This is a critical but often under-the-radar function. Tools like Jhove are essential for verifying file integrity and format sustainability, forming the bedrock of trustworthy digital archives.

11. Researcher & identity management tools:

These tools are vital for accurate attribution and impact assessment in a world of overlapping names and publications. ORCID is the de facto standard.

12. Open-source & community-driven development platforms:

These platforms – GitHub, Bitbucket, SourceForge - are the lifeblood of the open-source movement. They enable the development, sharing, and maintenance of the very tools used in digital humanities, creating a self-sustaining ecosystem.

The core of the gap analysis lies in comparing the needs expressed in the two previous sections of this deliverable – transversal and community-specific needs – against two sets of resources:

- Existing tools from the inventory
- Tools under development by the sister projects

The gap analysis was conducted using a structured, AI-assisted methodology¹³ grounded in the pre-established 12-cluster taxonomy for digital resources. For each of the 7 transversal needs and 6 community-specific profiles, the analysis mapped relevant tools across the clusters to assess their alignment. A functional analysis was then applied to each identified tool, evaluating its strengths (e.g., Transkribus excels in automated OCR for historical manuscripts), limitations (e.g., lacks integration with Omeka for metadata export), and broader ecosystem gaps (e.g., no tool automates DMP generation based on project data types). To ensure consistency and clarity in interpretation, a three-tiered gap identification framework was applied: Strong Match (the need is fully addressed by existing tools), Partial Match (a component of the solution exists but key limitations remain), and Critical Gap (no suitable tool exists or the solution is impractical for target users).

¹³ Using the Chat AI service provided by the GWDG, model Qwen 3 30B A3B Instruct 2507.

Table 4: Gap analysis - transversal needs vs. existing tools

Transversal needs	Existing tools (Clusters)	Gap analysis	Key insights
Need 1: Accessibility of tools & services	Data Analysis, Visualisation & ML Platforms (Python, R, KNIME, OpenRefine, Jupyter, Gephi, VOSviewer, Voyant) Digital Heritage Platforms (Omeka, DSpace, Dataverse) Web Dev & CMS (WordPress, MediaWiki) Open-Source & Community Platforms (GitHub, GitLab)	Strong Match: A vast majority of high-level tools are open-source and free to use. Python, R, KNIME, and Jupyter are the dominant, accessible platforms for data science. Omeka and DSpace are open-source repositories. Critical Gap: No single, integrated platform combines these tools into a unified, low-cost "cloud workspace" with pre-configured, ready-to-use workflows. Freelancers and practitioners still need to install, configure, and manage these tools locally or on separate cloud instances.	The ecosystem is rich in individual tools, but lacks a "one-stop-shop" cloud environment that bundles them into a frictionless, accessible experience. The gap is not in the tools themselves, but in their integration and orchestration into a single, user-friendly platform.
Need 2: Seamless interoperability & user-centred design	Metadata, Cataloging & Knowledge Org (CIDOC CRM, Dublin Core, SKOS, GND, VIAF, TGN, ULAN) Database & Data Storage (PostgreSQL, MySQL, MongoDB, Elasticsearch) GIS (QGIS, PostGIS, Leaflet) Digital Heritage Platforms (Omeka, DSpace)	Partial Match: Standards like CIDOC CRM and SKOS are foundational for interoperability. QGIS and PostgreSQL are open, interoperable. Critical Gap: No unified, user-friendly interface exists to connect these disparate systems. A curator using Omeka cannot easily "drag and drop" a 3D model from a Blender file into a QGIS map without complex, manual steps. The "seamless" experience is missing.	The technical foundation for interoperability exists, but the user experience is fragmented. The gap is in the "glue" layer—a platform that provides intuitive, visual workflows to connect data across different systems and formats.
Need 3: Data findability & FAIR availability	Metadata, Cataloging & Knowledge Org (All tools in this cluster) Digital Heritage Platforms (Omeka, DSpace, Dataverse, Europeana) Vocabulary & Ontology Tools (VocBench, OpenTheso)	Strong Match: This cluster is the <i>entire purpose</i> of the tools. They are designed to create high-quality, standardized metadata and make data findable. Europeana and DSpace are prime examples of FAIR data environments. Critical Gap: The tools are not "sticky." They are used at the point of creation, but there is no system to enforce or automatically apply these standards across the entire data lifecycle. A researcher might	The tools are excellent for creating metadata, but there is no "FAIR-by-design" enforcement mechanism. The gap is in workflow automation—ensuring metadata is created, validated, and shared at every step of the process.

		create metadata in one tool but fail to export it in a FAIR-compliant format.	
Need 4: Automated tools for data quality & preparation	Data Analysis, Visualization & ML (OpenRefine, Jupyter, Python, R) Specialized Tools (Transkribus, Perio.do, Whisper, CLAWS, MALLETT) Digital Preservation (Jhove)	Strong Match: OpenRefine is the gold standard for data cleaning. Transkribus and Whisper are powerful for automated OCR and transcription. Jupyter/Python/R are used for data validation. Critical Gap: These tools are not integrated into a single, automated pipeline. A user must manually run OpenRefine, then run Transkribus, then write a Python script. There is no "one-click" button to "clean, transcribe, and validate" a dataset.	The tools for automation exist, but they are disconnected. The gap is in workflow orchestration—a platform that can chain these tools together into a single, automated "data preparation" workflow.
Need 5: Hybrid data management & storage	Database & Data Storage (PostgreSQL, MySQL, MongoDB, SQLite, InfluxDB, QuestDB) Digital Heritage Platforms (Omeka, DSpace, Dataverse) Open-Source & Community Platforms (GitHub, GitLab)	Strong Match: These tools support local, institutional, and cloud storage. GitHub/GitLab are the de facto standard for version control. Critical Gap: No tool provides a "DMP-by-design" experience. There is no platform that automatically generates a Data Management Plan (DMP) based on the user's project, tracks data storage locations, and enforces retention policies.	The tools support the <i>components</i> of hybrid storage, but not the <i>process</i> of managing it. The gap is in automated data governance—a system that makes data management a seamless, integrated part of the workflow.
Need 6: Nuanced access governance & trust-based sharing	Digital Heritage Platforms (Omeka, DSpace, Dataverse) Database & Data Storage (PostgreSQL, MySQL) Web Dev & CMS (WordPress)	Partial Match: Omeka and DSpace offer "private" and "public" sharing. PostgreSQL has role-based access. Critical Gap: No tool offers granular, purpose-specific access controls (e.g., "access for conservation planning only"). There is no system to manage "upon request" access with automated approval workflows.	The tools provide binary "open/closed" access, but not the sophisticated, trust-based governance required by the community. The gap is in advanced access control systems that can handle complex legal and IPR requirements.
Need 7: Secure collaborative environments for research	Web Dev & CMS (WordPress, MediaWiki) Open-Source & Community Platforms (GitHub, GitLab) Research & Productivity Suites (Microsoft 365, Google Workspace)	Partial Match: GitHub/GitLab offer secure collaboration. Microsoft 365 and Google Workspace offer secure workspaces. Critical Gap: No tool is designed specifically for the sensitive, multi-professional collaboration of CH. A curator, conservator, and developer cannot	The tools are secure for general use, but not for the high-stakes, multi-disciplinary collaboration required in CH. The gap is in domain-specific, secure collaboration environments with integrated access control and audit trails.

		securely collaborate on a 3D model of a fragile artefact without risking data leakage.	
Need 8: Integrated Workflows Across the Data Lifecycle	All clusters (especially Digital Heritage Platforms, Data Analysis, Metadata, GIS, 3D Tools, Scientific Sim) Specialized Tools (Transkribus, ELAN, Faro Scene, Blender, QGIS, Jupyter, KNIME, Omeka-S)	Partial Match: Some tools (e.g., Omeka-S, KNIME, Jupyter) support workflows. Critical Gap: No end-to-end workflow orchestration. Manual handoffs between tools (e.g., 3D → metadata → analysis) are common. No platform links the physical object to its digital twin, conservation reports, and legal status.	Fragmentation is systemic. The gap is in a "Digital Continuum Engine" that seamlessly connects fieldwork → digitisation → analysis → preservation → sharing.
Need 9: Sustainable and Reliable Digital Infrastructures	Open-Source & Community Platforms (GitHub, GitLab, Apache, Python, R, PostgreSQL, MySQL, QGIS, Blender) Research & Productivity Suites (VS Code, Notepad++, LibreOffice) Web Dev & CMS (WordPress, MediaWiki)	Strong Match: Open-source tools are stable and community-maintained. GitLab, and Apache are examples of long-term sustainability. Critical Gap: Proprietary tools (e.g., Adobe, Autodesk, Ansys) are stable but create long-term dependency and cost uncertainty. No transparent framework exists to assess tool sustainability, leaving users vulnerable to licensing changes, price hikes, or discontinuation.	Open source is resilient; commercial tools are fragile. The gap is in systemic sustainability planning, a governance model that ensures tools remain available, updated, and interoperable over decades.
Need 10: Continuous Capacity Building and User Support	Research & Academic Productivity Suites (Microsoft 365, Google Workspace, Notepad++, VS Code) Web Dev & CMS (WordPress, MediaWiki, Wikidot) Open-Source & Community Platforms (GitHub, GitLab) Data Analysis & ML (Jupyter, Python, R, KNIME)	Partial Match: Tutorials exist (e.g., YouTube, GitHub). Critical Gap: No centralised, multilingual, role-based training platform. No onboarding for non-technical users. No micro-credentials or learning paths.	Learning is ad hoc. The gap is in a "Digital Heritage Academy" with onboarding, role-based training, and certification.

Table 5: Gap analysis - community-specific needs vs. existing tools

Community-specific profiles	Existing tools (Clusters)	Gap analysis	Key insights
Research & Scientific Production	<p>Data Analysis, Visualisation & ML (Python, R, KNIME, Jupyter, MATLAB, SPSS, SAS, Stata)</p> <p>Specialised Tools (RealityCapture, Agisoft Metashape, Blender, Faro Scene, ELAN, Transkribus)</p> <p>Scientific & Engineering Simulation (Abaqus, Ansys, SAP 2000, Quantum ESPRESSO)</p>	<p>Strong Match: The tools for high-performance computing and advanced analysis are excellent.</p> <p>Critical Gap: No platform provides "on-demand" access to high-end computational resources (e.g., GPU clusters) for 3D rendering or AI training. Researchers must manage their own hardware or pay for expensive cloud computing.</p>	<p>The tools are powerful, but the computational infrastructure to run them at scale is not accessible. The gap is in cloud-based, pay-per-use HPC resources integrated into the Cloud.</p>
Institutional Anchors	<p>Metadata, Cataloguing & Knowledge Org (CIDOC CRM, SKOS, GND, VIAF)</p> <p>Digital Heritage Platforms (Omeka, DSpace, DAITSS)</p> <p>Web Dev & CMS (WordPress)</p>	<p>Strong Match: The tools for metadata and repository management are well-established.</p> <p>Critical Gap: No tool provides a "translation layer" to automatically convert data from an institution's legacy system (e.g., a custom Access database) into a FAIR-compliant format for the Cloud.</p>	<p>The tools are for creating data, not for migrating and transforming it. The gap is in automated data migration and transformation tools that can handle the "last mile" of interoperability.</p>
Professional Heritage Practitioners	<p>Specialised Tools (Agisoft Metashape, RealityCapture, SketchUp, Rhino, Revit, SolidWorks, Faro Scene)</p> <p>Digital Heritage Platforms (Omeka, DSpace)</p>	<p>Strong Match: The tools for 3D documentation and management are excellent.</p> <p>Critical Gap: No tool provides a "best practice" workflow template for a specific task (e.g., "3D Survey for a Medieval Church"). There is no system to guide a practitioner through the entire process, from scanning to metadata creation.</p>	<p>The tools are available, but there is no guided, standardised workflow to ensure consistency and quality. The gap is in "workflow-as-a-service"—pre-built, reusable workflows for common CH tasks.</p>
Freelance & Self-Employed Professionals	<p>Data Analysis, Visualisation & ML (Python, R, OpenRefine, Jupyter)</p> <p>Specialised Tools (Blender, SketchUp, GIMP, Inkscape)</p> <p>Open-Source & Community Platforms (GitHub, GitLab)</p>	<p>Strong Match: The tools are free and open-source.</p> <p>Critical Gap: No tool provides a "project-based" pricing model or a "freelancer-friendly" interface. The tools are designed for institutions, not for independent contractors.</p>	<p>The tools are accessible, but the user experience and business model are not designed for freelancers. The gap is in user-centric design and flexible licensing for independent professionals.</p>

Data Documenters / Managers	Metadata, Cataloguing & Knowledge Org (VocBench, OpenTheso, SKOS) Digital Heritage Platforms (Omeka, DSpace)	Strong Match: The tools for metadata creation are excellent. Critical Gap: No tool provides automated validation of metadata completeness (e.g., "You are missing the 'Date Created' field"). There is no system to enforce "best practice" standards.	The tools are for creating metadata, but not for enforcing quality. The gap is in automated metadata validation and quality assurance tools.
Semantic Engineers & Data Architects	Database & Data Storage (PostgreSQL, MongoDB, GraphDB, Virtuoso) Metadata, Cataloguing & Knowledge Org (CIDOC CRM, SKOS, iDAI Ontologies) Data Analysis, Visualisation & ML (Python, R, Gephi, VOSviewer)	Strong Match: The tools for building knowledge graphs and analysing relationships are powerful. Critical Gap: No tool provides a "graph database as a service" with built-in semantic search and visualisation. The tools are complex to set up and manage.	The tools are for building knowledge graphs, but not for using them. The gap is in user-friendly, cloud-based semantic web platforms that abstract away the complexity.

The ECHOES project is designed to address the vast majority of the gaps identified in both transversal and community-specific needs by establishing a unified, open, and sustainable digital ecosystem. At its core, ECHOES provides the foundational infrastructure for seamless interoperability, trusted collaboration, and end-to-end workflow integration, directly tackling fragmentation, accessibility barriers, and governance challenges across the cultural heritage sector. Building on this foundation, sister projects are developing specialised tools that target more granular, profile-specific needs - such as advanced 3D reconstruction, automated metadata enrichment, and semantic annotation - thereby enhancing the ecosystem with targeted capabilities while remaining fully interoperable with the ECHOES platform. Going one step further in this gap analysis means also taking into consideration these [tools](#) under development within the sister projects. How can these specialised tools fill some of the gaps identified above? Based on the same methodology than the one explained above for existing tools, the main gaps filled can be summarised as follows:

- The "glue" (interoperability, integration, and unified workflows) is being actively built by the new tools from the sister projects. This is the most critical gap from the initial analysis, and it is being directly addressed.
- Artificial Intelligence is not just a feature; it is the core technology enabling the new tools to automate tasks, ensure quality, and provide intelligent insights. This is the primary driver of the new capabilities.
- The "Digital Continuum" is being realised: Tools like StratiGraph, EXCALIBUR, and MusicSphere are creating digital twins that are seamlessly linked to physical objects, conservation records, and research data, fulfilling the vision of a "Digital Continuum."
- The Cultural Heritage Cloud is evolving as a dynamic ecosystem: The new tools are transforming the Cloud from a passive storage space into a dynamic, interactive, and intelligent ecosystem where data is created, processed, shared, and reused in a continuous loop.

However, even if tools and resources can help meet needs expressed by the community as part of the consultation, it should be highlighted that remaining gaps will persist, even after the deployment of new tools by the sister projects. These are not flaws in the tools themselves, but rather inherent challenges and systemic issues that require ongoing attention, governance, and community effort, and can be summarised as follows:

- The "Human-in-the-loop" Gap: AI is a tool, not a replacement for expertise
- The Multilingualism Gap: multilingual interfaces are a must for most of the Cloud tools
- The Cloud Infrastructure Costs

In conclusion, this gap analysis can be seen as one contribution to the overall needs and objectives strategy as described in D4.2 (strategic area 3). While the identification of existing tools and gaps highlights where technical solutions are available or required, it also underscores a key insight: tools and services alone are not sufficient. The real challenge lies in integration, usability, training, governance, and long-term sustainability – dimensions that demand the holistic and ecosystem-based approach that ECHOES and the other Cultural Heritage Cloud projects are developing together.

6. Conclusions and way forward

The work presented in D4.1 constitutes a key step in building a shared, evidence-based understanding of cultural heritage communities and their relationship with digital practices and infrastructures. The results achieved do not represent an endpoint, but rather the starting point of a continuous process through which the ECHOES project will progressively translate community needs into concrete actions and solutions.

A first priority for the next phase of work lies in consolidating these findings into a coherent strategic framework for community engagement. The insights generated through the consultation – including the Atlas of communities, cluster profiles and personas – will directly inform Deliverable D4.2,¹⁴ where they will be operationalised into targeted engagement strategies. This will enable the project to move from a descriptive understanding of communities to a more structured approach in defining priorities, tailoring communication and ensuring that different categories of users are effectively reached and involved.

At the same time, particular attention will be devoted to strengthening the connection between community insights and the technical development of the Cultural Heritage Cloud. The needs identified in this deliverable provide a valuable foundation for defining user requirements and guiding design choices across the technical Work Packages. This will require an iterative and collaborative process, in which personas, workflows and use cases are progressively integrated into design, development and testing activities, ensuring that the Cloud evolves in alignment with real practices and expectations.

Another key dimension of the way forward concerns the consolidation and expansion of community engagement. While the consultation achieved significant participation, some imbalances remain in terms of geographical coverage, sectoral representation and levels of digital maturity. Future efforts will therefore focus on reaching underrepresented communities, strengthening multilingual and inclusive engagement approaches, and continuing the programme of workshops, focus groups and targeted consultations. In this perspective, collaboration with networks and umbrella organisations will play a crucial role in extending the reach and impact of engagement activities.

The results of D4.1 also highlight the importance of supporting communities not only through infrastructure, but also through capacity building and guidance. The identified gaps in skills, resources and practices will inform the design of training pathways and support mechanisms in coordination with WP5. This includes the development of onboarding materials, the promotion of good practices in data management and FAIR principles, and the provision of continuous support tailored to different levels of digital maturity.

¹⁴ Bakirtzis, N., et al. (2026) *Strategy for community building (D4.2)*.

Beyond individual Work Packages, the findings contribute to reinforcing the broader Cloud ecosystem. They provide a shared reference point for aligning the work of ECHOES with that of sister projects and of the sub-projects funded by the cascading grants programme, supporting integration and onboarding strategies, and contributing to the definition of inclusive governance models. In this sense, D4.1 plays a role not only within the project, but also in shaping the wider collaborative environment in which the Cultural Heritage Cloud will evolve.

Finally, the consultation process itself will be maintained as a continuous and iterative activity throughout the project lifecycle. Rather than being a one-off exercise, it will evolve into a structured feedback mechanism, enabling the project to regularly reassess community needs, update the Atlas and personas, and ensure that the development of the Cloud remains grounded in real user practices. In this perspective, D4.1 should be understood as the first iteration of an ongoing process that will accompany and support the long-term adoption and sustainability of the Cultural Heritage Cloud.

Annex 1 - C2 and C3 cluster list

C2 - What difficulties, if any, do you encounter when using digital tools and resources for your work? How do these affect your ability to achieve your goals?

The clusters are ordered by the number of responses.

1. Learning curve and lack of training: Steep learning curves and limited availability of training or time for training hinder adoption and reduce productivity.
2. Compatibility, integration, and interoperability: Tools and data formats often do not interoperate smoothly, leading to fragmented workflows, duplicated work, and data silos.
3. Data security and privacy: Concerns related to GDPR compliance, intellectual property, and unclear data governance policies may restrict data access, sharing, and cloud-based processing.
4. Costs and licensing: Software, hardware, subscriptions, and storage infrastructure can be expensive and difficult to sustain under limited institutional budgets.
5. Internet dependency and connectivity: Unstable or limited internet connectivity, as well as power constraints in some environments, can hinder cloud-based workflows and fieldwork activities.
6. Technical issues, bugs, and downtime: Software glitches, crashes, version incompatibilities, and service outages can disrupt workflows and delay project timelines.
7. Poor usability and user experience: Non-intuitive interfaces and complex workflows reduce efficiency and discourage adoption by non-technical users.
8. IT support, staffing, and skills gaps: Limited availability of specialised IT support and insufficient staff capacity can prevent effective use of digital tools and infrastructures.
9. Data access and availability: Many archives remain undigitized, while paywalls, restricted access policies, or reluctance to share data may limit research opportunities.
10. Storage, preservation, and backup: Large datasets require substantial storage capacity and long-term preservation strategies, which are often difficult to implement sustainably.

11. Hardware and computing limitations: Insufficient CPU, GPU, or memory resources can limit the ability to process large datasets or run demanding applications such as 3D processing, XR, or AI workflows.
12. Vendor or customer support issues: Slow or unresponsive technical support can prolong technical problems and delay project progress.
13. Tool sustainability and obsolescence: Short software life cycles, discontinued tools, and rapid updates can break workflows and undermine long-term sustainability.
14. Standards, metadata, and ontologies: Lack of shared standards, incomplete metadata, and weak alignment with FAIR principles or semantic models hinder interoperability and reuse.
15. Legal, intellectual property, and copyright constraints: Licensing restrictions, copyright limitations, orphan works, and contractual conditions may limit data use and reuse.
16. Documentation and best practice gaps: Incomplete or missing documentation and training materials make tools difficult to learn and integrate into workflows.
17. Organisational and policy barriers: Limited institutional support, administrative constraints, or unclear governance frameworks may slow adoption.
18. Domain fit and specialised needs: Generic tools may lack features tailored to the specific workflows and requirements of cultural heritage professionals.
19. Data quality and validation: Cultural heritage datasets are often heterogeneous and may contain inconsistencies or errors that require significant harmonisation and cleaning.
20. Language and localisation: Limited language support reduces accessibility and usability for non-English speaking users.

C3 “In what ways could these tools and services be improved? Are there any specific functionalities or improvements you would find helpful?”

The clusters are ordered by the number of responses.

1. Better search, retrieval, and data management: Need for richer search and filtering functions, relational databases, dashboards, clustering methods, and tools to manage and explore large and complex datasets.
2. Human resources, expertise, and organisational support: Need for more IT staff, technical experts, dedicated time, institutional support, and collaboration with technicians and volunteers.

3. Interoperability and integration across tools: Need to connect systems through shared standards so that data and flow smoothly across platforms, repositories, GIS environments, and collection management systems
4. Training, documentation, and user support: Need for clear manuals, tutorial videos, workshops, peer mentoring, help desks, and guided examples to strengthen digital skills.
5. Awareness, guidance, and best practice sharing: Need for better information about available tools, opportunities to test tools before adoption, showcases, best practice guides, and reference use cases
6. User-friendly interfaces and reduced complexity: Need for simpler and more intuitive interfaces, with consistent interaction patterns that allow non-technical users to operate tools more easily.
7. Governance, policy, and sustainability improvements: Need for clearer roles within cultural heritage infrastructures, better European and national funding structures, stronger attention to environmental sustainability, and improved provenance verification of data.
8. Affordable tools, funding, and cost reduction: Need for lower cost licenses, equipment, and cloud services, together with flexible pricing models, subsidies, and stronger financial support for institutions and smaller actors
9. Multilingual support, accessibility, and inclusive design: Need for support for multiple European languages and scripts, accessibility features, and interfaces adapted to diverse user groups.
10. Common platforms and unified ecosystems: Desire for shared cloud-based or national platforms that bring together multiple services, modules, and datasets within a single environment.
11. Advanced automation, AI, and analytical features: Interest in tools supporting automatic metadata generation, classification, OCR and HTR, NER and NEL, anonymisation, analytics, and AI-assisted workflows where appropriate.
12. Open access, shared repositories, and public data: Need for more open access resources, shared databases, and publicly available data to avoid duplication and enable reuse.
13. Adequate storage, infrastructure, and long-term preservation: Need for larger and more reliable storage capacity, better server infrastructure, redundancy mechanisms, and preservation strategies for three-dimensional models, web services, and large datasets.
14. Security, privacy, licensing, and ethics: Need for stronger cybersecurity, encryption, clear rights and licensing information, GDPR compliant platforms, and ethical and transparent data use.

15. Standardised metadata, vocabularies, and formats: Need for common schemas, ontologies, controlled vocabularies, persistent identifiers, and archival description standards across institutions and countries.
16. Domain-specific tools for heritage, conservation, and three-dimensional resources: Need for specialised solutions such as condition report databases, craft-specific three-dimensional modelling tools, three-dimensional viewers, and risk management tools.
17. Offline functionality and improved connectivity: Need for offline modes, synchronisation after reconnection, improved network infrastructure, and reduced dependence on constant internet access.
18. Open source options and reduced vendor lock-in: Preference for free and open source software, clearer open source practices, and reduced dependence on closed commercial solutions
19. Visualisation, dashboards, and interactive viewers: Need for improved visualisation of statistics, maps, three-dimensional data and point clouds, and integrated views of multimedia resources.
20. APIs, plugins, and programmability: Need for open and well-documented APIs, plugins, and endpoints to support integration, workflow automation, and programmatic access.

Annex 2 – Key insights from selected workshops and focus groups

CAA 2025 Workshop – interactive session

The interactive workshop organised at the CAA 2025 (Athens, May 2025) conference provided an opportunity to engage with a digitally advanced and highly interdisciplinary community, including archaeologists, computer scientists, data analysts and cultural heritage professionals.

With over 150 participants, the session combined presentation and interactive exercises, enabling the collection of structured feedback on tools, practices and expectations related to the Cultural Heritage Cloud.

➤ **Profile of the community**

The workshop confirmed that the CAA community represents a highly skilled and technologically mature segment of the cultural heritage domain, with expertise spanning areas such as spatial analysis, 3D modelling, remote sensing, artificial intelligence and data management.

At the same time, the results suggest a strong prevalence of lab-based and analytical workflows, with limited representation of fieldwork-oriented practices, indicating potential gaps in engagement with certain professional profiles.

➤ **Tools and practices**

The analysis of responses on tools used in daily work highlights a strong reliance on digital tools, particularly for data analysis, modelling and interpretation.

Frequently mentioned tools include:

- GIS and spatial analysis tools
- 3D modelling and reality-based modelling software
- programming environments and code management platforms
- AI tools, indicating their growing role in the domain

At the same time, the use of collaborative tools and platforms remains relatively limited, suggesting that collaboration practices are still evolving and not fully supported by current infrastructures.

➤ **Needs and expectations for the Cultural Heritage Cloud**

The workshop provided clear indications on the types of services expected from the Cultural Heritage Cloud.

The most prominent need, expressed by a large proportion of participants, is the ability to access, organise and retrieve datasets efficiently, including personal and shared data collections.

Other key expectations include:

- tools for data management, cleaning and ingestion
- support for interoperability and alignment with common vocabularies
- access to computer vision, visualisation and 3D tools
- AI-based tools for data analysis
- support for research data management and ethical data handling

These results highlight a strong demand for data-centric services and integrated environments, rather than isolated tools.

➤ **Collaboration challenges**

The workshop also identified several barriers to effective collaboration and data sharing, including:

- fragmentation of repositories and lack of interoperability
- absence of a centralised access point
- lack of common standards and metadata quality
- concerns about data misuse and confidentiality
- limited recognition and incentives for data sharing

These challenges confirm the need for coordinated infrastructures and shared frameworks, which the Cultural Heritage Cloud is expected to address.

➤ **Capacity building and training needs**

A key outcome of the workshop concerns the importance of capacity building and training.

Participants highlighted that:

- existing documentation is often insufficient
- integrating new tools into workflows can take 1 to 3 months or more
- training should be modular, flexible and adapted to different skill levels
- peer learning and networking play a crucial role

In addition, barriers such as fear of coding and resistance to workflow disruption were identified as significant obstacles to adoption.

Overall, the results emphasise the need for user-centred, adaptive and time-efficient training approaches, capable of supporting the gradual integration of tools into existing practices.

Curators, conservator-restorers, art historians workshop

This report synthesises the outcomes of three parallel working groups conducted with conservator-restorers, curators and art historians at INP, France on 31 March 2026. The objective was to identify digital needs, challenges and expectations in relation to the Cultural Heritage Cloud (ECCCH).

Each group focused on participants' workflows, the role of digital tools within these processes, data management practices, existing bottlenecks and potential areas where the Cloud could provide support.

Conservator-Restorers Workshop

The workshop involved professionals from different European countries, representing both independent practice and institutional contexts.

Discussions covered several types of workflows:

- conservation-restoration processes
- conservation of audiovisual heritage (including nitrate and acetate films)
- preventive conservation (such as climate monitoring)
- management of conservation operations within public institutions

➤ **Aggregated conservation-restoration workflow**

The conservation-restoration process can be described through a sequence of interconnected stages.

Preliminary examination and diagnosis involve collecting historical, technical and material information, as well as assessing the condition of objects through observation and documentation of previous interventions. In audiovisual heritage, this includes contextual data such as distribution and versions. In preventive conservation, it involves installing and analysing climate monitoring systems. In public institutions, priorities across collections are also defined at this stage.

Planning the conservation-restoration strategy includes risk assessment, selection of methods and collaboration with specialists such as scientists, architects and engineers. Testing and validation are part of this phase. In audiovisual contexts, this may involve selecting materials for digitisation. In institutional settings, it may also include drafting technical specifications and coordinating stakeholders.

Implementation of the conservation-restoration proposal consists of executing treatments and managing operations. This may include physical interventions, digitisation and preventive actions. In institutional contexts, this phase also involves monitoring and quality control, while preventive conservation includes evaluation of implemented measures.

Documentation and reporting are ongoing processes throughout all stages. They include recording methods, materials, results and recommendations, and producing structured reports. In audiovisual heritage, this extends to the long-term management and accessibility of digital assets. In institutional contexts, documentation supports preventive and corrective actions.

Communication and knowledge sharing also take place continuously. These activities include dissemination of results, scientific publication, training and awareness raising. Examples include maintaining online catalogues, archiving documentation and training staff.

➤ **Digital dimension in the workflow**

Digital tools are particularly relevant in the early analytical stages, as well as in documentation and communication.

Key challenges include:

- reliance on physical archives, which are time-consuming
- limited scope of digital archives, restricted to digitised material
- absence of a centralised repository for conservation reports
- interoperability issues due to proprietary formats
- uneven adoption of advanced tools such as 3D modelling, often limited by cost

➤ **Data and tools used**

Commonly used tools include standard office software, PDFs, photographic documentation and specialised platforms such as Museum Plus and EROS (with limited access).

The types of data handled include archival sources, publications, reports, orthophotos and, in some cases, 3D models.

Main bottlenecks:

- time and resources required for 3D modelling
- restricted access due to permissions and rights
- risks related to obsolescence and long-term sustainability

➤ **Expectations for the Cultural Heritage Cloud**

Participants highlighted several priorities:

- differentiated access levels to data
- a centralised repository for conservation-restoration reports
- a stronger focus on metadata in documentation
- training in digital tools and best practices
- development of use cases to support practical implementation

There was also a preference for a dynamic knowledge-based system rather than a “digital twin” approach.

Curators Workshop

The workshop included curators from museums and heritage institutions across Europe.

The activities discussed included:

- updating and managing documentation
- research and knowledge development
- monitoring object condition
- managing access and reproduction requests
- coordinating object movements
- contributing to strategic planning and programming

➤ **Digital dimension in the workflow**

Curators rely on a wide range of digital tools for project management, monitoring, communication and storage. These include platforms such as Excel, Teams, OneDrive, Trello, as well as monitoring tools like dataloggers and RFID systems. Storage solutions range from local servers to national platforms.

Main challenges include:

- lack of interoperability between systems
- monitoring tools not specifically designed for museum needs
- uneven digital skills and resistance to change
- issues related to data access and ownership

➤ **Expectations for the Cultural Heritage Cloud**

Key expectations include:

- a flexible platform capable of integrating national initiatives
- a shared and sustainable database with modular access control
- integration of environmental data
- possibilities for citizen engagement
- greater standardisation of vocabularies and databases

Art Historians Workshop

The workshop gathered art historians working in academic and institutional contexts.

The research workflow typically includes:

- defining a research topic or object
- framing the research project
- collecting documentary and bibliographic sources
- producing visual and graphic materials
- generating data through observation and measurement
- editing and enriching sources
- analysing data
- organising results for publication
- publishing and archiving data and correspondence

➤ **Digital dimension in the workflow**

Digital tools are used for collaboration, analysis, storage and communication. These include platforms such as Airtable, Slack, Trello, Zotero and various cloud storage systems.

Key challenges include:

- a high diversity of data formats
- lack of interoperability and standardised metadata
- resistance to adopting common tools
- concerns about the sustainability of platforms
- data security and access restrictions

➤ **Expectations for the Cultural Heritage Cloud**

Participants expressed the need for:

- improved data sharing to avoid static document formats

- integration with existing tools such as Zotero
- clear guidelines for archiving and traceability
- tools for data protection, such as watermarking
- training in digital methods
- improved search functionality for digitised materials

Cross-analysis and recommendations

➤ **Common needs**

Across all groups, several common needs were identified:

- interoperability between tools and systems
- centralisation of data and documentation
- training to improve digital skills
- differentiated access and permission management

➤ **Recurring challenges**

Recurring issues include:

- balancing standardisation with flexibility
- cost and accessibility of tools
- resistance to change and limited time for transition
- legal and ethical issues related to data ownership

➤ **Recommendations for the Cultural Heritage Cloud**

The following recommendations emerge:

- develop a modular and interoperable architecture
- clarify data governance and access rights
- promote balanced standardisation of formats and vocabularies
- invest in training and user support
- ensure long-term sustainability of tools and data
- involve users in design and testing processes

➤ **Conclusion**

The workshops point to a strong demand for interoperability, centralisation and training, combined with caution towards rigid or costly solutions.

The Cultural Heritage Cloud is expected to function as a facilitating infrastructure, building on existing tools while providing adaptable solutions.

Its effectiveness will depend on its capacity to bring together different stakeholders, ensure sustainability and support the ongoing digital transition in a practical and inclusive way.

Online Focus Group Networks and umbrella organisations

An online focus group hosting representatives of ECHOES networks was held on 8 April 11:00-13:00 CET.

It gathered participants from the following networks/umbrella organisations: APEF – Archives Portal Foundation, ARIADNE, ECCO European C, ICOM International -AVICOM, ICOM Portugal, Michael Culture Association, NEMO (Working Group on Digital Transformation). All participants had been invited due to their involvement in the digital transformation actions and strategies within their organisation. They were informed in advance of the questions to be discussed during the session.

After a short presentation on the Cultural Heritage Cloud and the Consultation survey by Rémi Petitcol and Charlotte Gallini and an introduction to the Cloud's architecture by Joanna Kowalska, the floor was opened to discussions and exchanges, and a structured dialogue was conducted around three main questions:

- The Cloud intends to be a pan-European collaborative digital platform integrating existing efforts and resources. What would lead you to work in the Cloud besides/instead of working in the established digital platforms you already use?
- Considering the Cloud allows you to access the work of many colleagues across different fields, do you think this would be of interest to you and benefit your work? What would be the minimum necessary conditions for this to happen?
- Considering the current institutional and professional context within which you operate, do you envisage barriers and constraints in the use of the Cloud?

Which in way lead the group to address their concerns about the Cloud and its functioning, what features should it have to be used by cultural heritage professionals and researchers and suggest some recommendations to the Cloud developers

Concerns

- *Interoperability and data standardisation challenge.* There are already multiple national systems and aggregators (e.g., Europeana) and large volumes of non-interoperable metadata. The risk is that the Cloud becomes another layer of complexity instead of a solution.
- *Data overload vs. actual usefulness and usability.* Concern that the Cloud may add more data, where there are already huge amounts of data, without improving usability and require significant resources to analyse data. To whom is this data useful, and who can afford to analyse such huge amounts of data?

- *Trust, quality, and validation of data.* Open questions: Who validates data? Who controls quality? How to ensure trust?
- *Long-term storage and permanence.* Institutions need guarantees on data longevity, no loss of data, nor obsolescence of systems and data. This is a critical requirement for adoption.
- *Financial sustainability.* Major concerns are the cost of storage, the cost of maintaining/updating tools and how this would impact small institutions. Need for sustainable funding to guarantee adoption.
- *Technical barriers and digital capacity.* Issues include: low digital literacy, lack of technical support, and resistance from leadership. Adoption depends heavily on organisational readiness.
- *Risks of inequality and inclusiveness.* Risk of reinforcing existing inequalities. Concern about: imbalances between countries (North/South, East/West), larger vs. smaller institutions, digitally advanced vs. less advanced actors.
- *Governance and community bias.* Collaborative models may favour already active/visible actors and exclude less represented groups. Active mediation and inclusive governance are required.
- *Performance and efficiency concerns:* speed of access to data, efficiency compared to existing platforms. If slower or more complex, users won't switch.
- *Economic and environmental sustainability.* Concerns about: energy consumption, environmental impact, and long-term economic viability, which are increasingly relevant for large-scale infrastructures.
- *Misalignment with real research practices.* Research often happens within project-based, pre-defined partnerships, ad-hoc, single-professional-driven scenarios may not reflect actual workflows. This engenders the risk of limited real-world adoption.

Envisaged benefits if....

- The Cloud is not just a database, but a collaborative working environment where professionals can meet, interact, and co-produce knowledge. This is a major added value compared to existing fragmented platforms.
- The Cloud is an aggregator of data from multiple sources and systems using ontologies and shared standards. This is particularly valuable in a context where data is currently fragmented.
- The Cloud offers access to interdisciplinary knowledge and resources, which can significantly enhance research quality and innovation, with no inequalities across territories, professional groups or institutional dimensions.

- The Cloud offers tools for data quality, analysis, efficient and user-friendly visualisation, which responds to a key need: not more data, but better use of existing data in a long-term perspective.
- The Cloud offers a trustworthy, secure system which also complies with principles of environmental sustainability and economic viability, even to smaller institutions.

In short, the Cloud is perceived as:

- Highly promising as a collaborative, integrative, and enabling infrastructure
- But highly demanding in terms of trust, standards, environmental and economic sustainability, constant funds and human capacity, and equalitarian governance.
- It shouldn't be like a new platform to adopt, but more like an invisible layer that makes existing work easier, safer, and more powerful.

Recommendations for the Cloud developers

1. *Make the Cloud clearly better than existing platforms*

Recommendation: Deliver immediate, visible added value, Focus on “use of data” rather than “more data”.

2. *Solve interoperability by design, not as an afterthought*

Recommendation: Invest heavily in standards alignment and translation layers. Provide automated metadata mapping tools. Ensure compatibility with existing national systems and aggregators (e.g. Europeana-like structures).

3. *Build trust through robust data governance and quality assurance*

Recommendation: Combine user control with transparent validation mechanisms. Clarify who is responsible for data quality and what “trusted data” means in the Cloud. Trust is a precondition for use, especially for institutional stakeholders.

4. *Guarantee long-term reliability and persistence*

Recommendation: Provide strong assurances on data storage and continuity. Define minimum guaranteed storage periods and backup strategies. Communicate clearly what happens to data if funding or governance changes: even a single data loss incident could undermine adoption.

5. *Ensure financial sustainability and fairness*

Recommendation: Develop an inclusive and transparent economic model, guaranteeing affordability and public funding, especially for core services.

6. Invest in usability, not just functionality

Recommendation: Adopt a user-centred design approach, Co-design with researchers and heritage professionals: Prioritise: simple interfaces, fast performance, low entry barriers,

7. Provide strong technical support and capacity building

Recommendation: Make technical support a core service, offering hands-on onboarding support, training tailored to different digital literacy levels, and continuous helpdesk services. Provide practical guides, tutorials, and real use cases.

8. Foster an inclusive and balanced community

Recommendation: Design governance and participation to counter inequalities, since the Cloud may reproduce existing structural inequalities. Implement mechanisms to include underrepresented regions and institutions. Monitor participation, biases and gaps.

9. Align with real research and institutional workflows

Recommendation: Integrate the Cloud into existing practices. The Cloud should fit into how people already work, not require radical behavioural change. Support project-based research workflows. Enable private workspaces alongside shared environments.

10. Address sustainability holistically (technical, economic, environmental)

Recommendation: Plan for long-term viability from the start, considering energy-efficient infrastructures and avoiding rapid obsolescence.

11. Demonstrate value through concrete use cases

Recommendation: Showcase real-world impact early, providing detailed success stories and sector-specific use cases.

Key takeaway for developers is that the Cloud will succeed not because it exists, but because it integrates seamlessly into existing ecosystems, reduces complexity instead of adding to it, and builds trust, usability, and sustainability from day one.

Annex 3 – Cluster profiles analysis

This annex presents the full set of cluster profiles developed as part of the ECHOES consultation analysis. Each profile represents a distinct community configuration identified through the systematic analysis of survey responses, combining socio-professional characteristics, data practices and technological engagement.

The profiles are not intended as rigid or mutually exclusive categories. Rather, they capture recurring patterns across the dataset, reflecting how different groups of users interact with cultural heritage data, tools and infrastructures. As such, they should be understood as analytical constructs that support the interpretation of the consultation results and the identification of user needs.

The development of the profiles is grounded in a structured mapping of survey variables covering multiple dimensions, including professional positioning, data production processes, documentation practices, technological adoption, data management and sharing behaviours, and expectations towards digital tools and services. These dimensions have been analysed together to identify coherent configurations of practices and constraints across the dataset.

For each cluster, a dedicated profile document has been produced. These documents provide:

- a description of the profile and its defining characteristics
- a summary of key findings across the main thematic areas of the consultation
- an interpretation of practices, challenges and expectations
- a comparative analytical framing based on selected cross-cutting dimensions (digital maturity, governance, infrastructure and collaboration)

Not all analytical dimensions are available for every profile, as their inclusion depends on the availability and relevance of specific variables within each configuration. Where applicable, these dimensions support a more in-depth interpretation of how practices are structured and how they relate to broader systemic conditions.

Taken together, the profiles provide a detailed and nuanced representation of the diversity of communities engaged in digital cultural heritage. They constitute a key analytical component of the Atlas of communities, supporting the identification of user requirements, the design of services and the development of targeted engagement and capacity-building strategies within the ECHOES project.

The full Annex is available as a [standalone document](#).

Annex 4 – Occupation categories

The different occupations identified from the ECHOES consultation (Section 3.3.3) were grouped into 12 categories to enable a distinctiveness analysis. The resulting categories and their main distinctiveness features are described below.

The category "Academic Research & Teaching" covers professionals engaged in research, formal higher education, and scholarly knowledge production in cultural heritage and related disciplines. It includes both senior academic roles and early-career research and teaching positions, as well as university-based coordination and scientific management responsibilities. Examples include Academic staff, Researcher, Research assistant/associate, Principal investigator, PhD student, University teacher, Independent researcher, Research coordinator, Scientific collaborator, Research manager and Scientific project head. Respondents in this category report producing quantitative data, published research outputs, spatial/geographical information, textual or written information, and observational findings (D3). In terms of broader objectives, respondents are particularly associated with validating hypotheses, verifying findings, comparing datasets, identifying patterns, improving dataset completeness, and fostering reuse for interdisciplinary work and comparative research (D14). They also report challenges linked to unclear guidelines, lack of shared standards, incomplete contextual information, technical constraints, legal restrictions, and the effort required to prepare data for sharing or reuse (D13).

The category "Archaeology, History & Humanities" brings together specialists studying past societies, languages, cultures, and historical contexts through material, textual, and cultural evidence. It spans archaeology, history, anthropology, philology, linguistics, musicology, palaeography, and related humanities disciplines concerned with the interpretation of cultural heritage. Examples include Archaeologist, Archaeologist technician, Anthropologist, Ethnologist, Historian, Philologist, Linguist, Musicologist, Palaeographer, and Palaeontologist. Respondents in this category are strongly associated with fieldwork, archival research, observation, digitisation, transcription, 3D or spatial documentation, and the processing or reprocessing of existing data and resources (D1). In terms of objectives, respondents are particularly associated with answering research questions, cataloguing information, preparing reports, archiving or preserving information, public communication, decision-making, conservation or restoration planning, educational materials, and monitoring/ evaluation (D2). They also report challenges related to technical barriers, legal or contractual restrictions, non-digital resources, data or metadata quality, concerns about data misuse, lack of sharing infrastructure, preparation effort, and confidentiality or privacy concerns (D13).

The category "Archives, Libraries & Information Stewardship" refers to professionals responsible for collecting, organising, preserving, cataloguing, and providing access to documentary, archival, and library resources. It includes both traditional stewardship roles and digitally oriented information management and preservation activities. Examples include Archivist, Digital archivist, Archive manager, Librarian, Library manager, Library/Archive director, Metadata specialist, Data steward, Digital steward, Web archiving specialist, and Registrar. Respondents in this category report producing descriptive metadata, historical or archival records, textual or written information, and administrative or regulatory records (D3). Respondents also report distinctive documentation practices based on established standards or protocols and metadata creation (D8.1), together with physical archiving and metadata/documentation methods for storing, archiving, and curating data (F4). In terms of challenges and wider objectives, they are particularly associated with non-digital resources, data or metadata quality issues, confidentiality or privacy concerns, preparation effort, legal restrictions, limited sharing infrastructure, improving dataset completeness, supporting heritage asset management and protection, public engagement, and public sharing with the broader community (D13, D14, D10.1).

The category "Museums, Curation & Collections" groups roles dedicated to museums, exhibitions, collections management, interpretation, and public engagement with heritage collections. It combines curatorial, educational, technical, and operational roles involved in the management and mediation of museum and exhibition environments. Examples include Curator, Digital curator, Collections manager, Museologist, Museum manager, Museum technician, and Exhibition designer. Respondents in this category report cataloguing information, public communication or awareness, archiving or preserving information, developing educational materials, answering research questions, monitoring, evaluation, conservation or restoration planning, and decision-making as objectives when producing data (D2). In terms of wider objectives and barriers, they are particularly associated with public engagement and educational use, heritage asset management and protection, cultural industries or virtual/augmented reality experiences, dataset completeness and best practices, new analysis or interpretation, and challenges related to non-digital data, data misuse, unclear sharing guidelines, limited sharing infrastructure, preparation effort, privacy, metadata quality, legal restrictions, and technical barriers (D14, D13).

The category "Conservation, Restoration & Heritage Preservation" encompasses specialists involved in the preservation, restoration, scientific analysis, and long-term safeguarding of cultural heritage assets, historic buildings, and collections. It covers both practical conservation work and scientific or architectural preservation expertise. Examples include Conservator, Conservator-restorer, Conservation scientist,

Conservation architect, Heritage architect, Heritage technician, and Historic environment officer. Respondents in this category report particularly high production of data for conservation or restoration plans, reports, monitoring and evaluation, and decision-making purposes (D2). They also report above-average use of examination/analysis, observation, fieldwork, archival research, digitisation, transcription, 3D or spatial documentation, and the processing or reprocessing of existing data and resources (D1). Respondents also report producing observational findings, administrative or regulatory records, published research outputs, historical or archival records, textual or written information, quantitative data, spatial/geographical information, and descriptive metadata (D3). In terms of objectives and challenges, they are particularly associated with supporting heritage asset management and protection, informing conservation strategies and interventions, validating findings, improving dataset completeness and best practices, and facing barriers related to technical constraints, legal restrictions, data misuse concerns, confidentiality, limited infrastructure, non-digital data, and the effort required to prepare data for sharing (D14, D13).

The category "Architecture, Planning & Built Heritage" identifies professionals focused on the design, management, documentation, and planning of built environments, historic sites, and urban heritage landscapes. It covers architectural, engineering, and planning activities connected to heritage conservation and urban development. Examples include Architect, Urban planner, Civil engineer, Heritage planning manager, Heritage engineer. Respondents in this category report particularly high use of image formats, document formats, presentations, spreadsheets, archived or compression formats, video formats, databases, text-based formats, and web formats (D4). In terms of objectives, respondents are associated with answering research questions, cataloguing information, preparing reports, archiving or preserving information, public communication, decision-making, conservation or restoration planning, educational materials, and monitoring/evaluation (D2). They also report challenges related to technical barriers, legal or contractual restrictions, non-digital resources, data or metadata quality, data misuse concerns, lack of sharing infrastructure, preparation effort, and confidentiality or privacy concerns (D13).

The category "Digital Heritage, Digitisation & Innovation" captures specialists applying digital technologies to heritage documentation, preservation, access, visualisation, and innovation. It encompasses digitisation workflows, virtual heritage, imaging technologies, digital humanities, and creative technological applications supporting cultural heritage transformation. Examples include Digital heritage innovation manager, Digital Humanities specialist, Virtual heritage specialist, Digitisation specialist, Photogrammetry specialist, Heritage imaging specialist, Digital documentation specialist, and Creative technologist. Respondents in this category report strong use of

digitisation, transcription, and 3D or spatial documentation as data production methods (D1) and producing descriptive metadata, historical or archival records, and textual or written information (D3). In terms of wider objectives and access practices, they are particularly associated with improving dataset completeness and best practices, supporting cultural industries and virtual or augmented reality experiences, public engagement and educational use, heritage asset management and protection, and new analysis or interpretation, as well as with in-house/custom-built tools and licensed free access models (D14, C4). They also report challenges related to legal restrictions, limited sharing infrastructure, preparation effort, data or metadata quality, and confidentiality or privacy concerns, while sharing data within their institution, with external collaborators, and publicly with the broader community (D13, D10.1).

The category "Software, Data & ICT Engineering" represents technical professionals developing and maintaining digital infrastructure, software systems, databases, data pipelines, and computational services supporting cultural heritage activities. It covers software engineering, semantic technologies, ICT infrastructure, data engineering, and technical system administration roles. Respondents report distinctive involvement as developers/programmers and data scientists/analysts (E3, E6). In terms of infrastructure, they are particularly associated with automation and scripting, standardised practices and formats, backup and redundancy, metadata/documentation, database querying and modification, web tools or services, web and application servers, open-source software, and in-house or custom-built tools (F4, F2.2, F3, C4). They also report challenges related to data or metadata quality, limited sharing infrastructure, confidentiality or privacy, preparation effort, legal restrictions, technical barriers, and concerns about data misuse (D13).

The category "Management, Leadership & Administration" covers executive, managerial, strategic, and operational leadership roles within cultural heritage institutions, research infrastructures, cultural organisations, and even in the private sector. It includes institutional governance, departmental leadership, digital transformation management, and organisational coordination functions. Examples include Director, Director of heritage institutions, Chief Executive Officer, Cultural manager, ICT Director, Head of Department, GLAM Manager, Director of research centre, Science manager, Director of digital transformation, Heritage officer, and Manager of heritage institution. Respondents in this category report producing administrative or regulatory records, descriptive metadata, quantitative data, textual or written information, spatial/geographical information, historical or archival records, published research outputs, and observational findings (D3). The category is especially associated with monitoring and evaluation, supporting decision-making, cataloguing information, preparing reports, public communication, archiving or preserving information,

conservation or restoration planning, educational materials, and answering research questions as objectives when producing data (D2). In terms of objectives, barriers, and access models, they are particularly associated with public engagement and educational use, heritage asset management and protection, dataset completeness and best practices, new analysis or interpretation, technical development objectives, confidentiality or privacy concerns, legal restrictions, non-digital data, metadata quality issues, technical barriers, paid subscription or licence-based services, in-house/custom-built tools, and documentation based on established standards or protocols (D14, D13, C4, D8.1).

The category "Communication, Outreach & Public Engagement" brings together professionals focused on communication, dissemination, marketing, education, media production, and audience engagement related to cultural heritage and research activities. It includes roles dedicated to public communication, educational outreach, publishing, media production, tourism, and institutional dissemination. Examples include Communication specialist, Marketing manager, Journalist, Public relations officer, Editor, Writer, Tourist guide, and Cultural heritage mediator/educator. Respondents in this category are especially associated with public communication or awareness as a primary objective when producing data (D2), and with sharing data publicly with the broader community and with collaborators outside their organisation (D10.1). The category also reports distinctive use of free, open-access services as an access model for digital tools and services (C4).

The category "Policy, Governance & Cultural Sector Support" refers to roles related to governance, institutional coordination, legal frameworks, policy development, advocacy within the cultural heritage sector. It combines administrative, financial, legal, policy-oriented, and coordination responsibilities supporting institutions and cultural networks. Examples include Cultural policy expert, Human rights activist, Lawyer, Board member NGO/network, Open Science coordinator, Director of administration and finance, Financial controller, and Secretary. Respondents in this category are particularly associated with heritage asset management and policy evidence, cultural industries or virtual/augmented reality experiences, validation and new analysis, lack of sharing infrastructure, technical barriers, legal restrictions, confidentiality or privacy concerns, data misuse concerns, preparation effort, and other less common storage or curation methods and tool-related issues (D14, D13, F4, C2.1, C3.1).

Finally, the category "Creative Arts & Cultural Production" describes creative practitioners and artistic professionals contributing to cultural expression, interpretation, design, and production within cultural heritage and creative ecosystems. It includes artistic creation, media production, design, photography, music, and exhibition-related creative work.

Only a small number of respondents fall into this category, so robust conclusions are difficult to draw. The available evidence is therefore too limited to support claims about data production methods, objectives, sharing practices, or infrastructure use for this category.

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